

ANIPH Data Libraries/D2.8

WP 2, T 2.5 Development of ANIPH AI predictive system and traceability tool

Authors: Marianna Kotzabasaki, Konstantina Filippou, Nikos Sotiropoulos and Chrysanthos Maraveas, AUA (Lead)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical references

Project Acronym	ANIPH
Project Title	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
Project Coordinator	ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL DE INVESTIGACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADOY DEL PLÁSTICO DE LA REGION DE MURCIA CETEC Carmen Fernández: c.fernandez@ctcalzado.org
Project Duration	January 2025 – December 2028 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D2.8
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 2 - ANIPH Project Baseline
Task	T2.5
Lead beneficiary	Partner 3 – AUA (Agricultural University of Athens)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	NA
Due date of deliverable	31/12/2025
Actual submission date	17/12/2025

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project’s page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

V	Date	Comments	Author/Reviewer
V0	26/11/2025	First draft of document	Marianna Kotzabasaki, Konstantina Filippou, Nikos Sotiropoulos (AUA) /Chrysanthos Maraveas (AUA)
V1	05/12/2025	Revised version based on the comments of the internal reviewers	Marianna Kotzabasaki, Konstantina Filippou, Nikos Sotiropoulos (AUA) / Chrysanthos Maraveas (AUA), Pablo Alarcón (UGR), Jaime Ortiz (CETEC)
VF	17/12/2025	Final version, approved by the project coordinator and submitted to EC	Marianna Kotzabasaki, Konstantina Filippou, Nikos Sotiropoulos (AUA) / Carmen Fernández, Cristina Blaya (CETEC)

Table of Contents

List of Tables	4
List of Figures	6
List of abbreviations	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
2. Methodology.....	12
2.1. Case study for PHAs Toxicity Data Libraries.....	13
2.1.1. Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV formulations)	18
2.1.2. Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV formulations).....	22
2.1.3. Cyto/Ecotoxicity Data Library of mcl-PHA-based formulations.....	27
2.2. Case study for PHAs Biodegradation Data Libraries	30
2.2.1. Biodegradation Data Library of PHA-based formulations	32
2.2.2. Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations.....	34
2.2.3. Biodegradation Data Library of mcl-PHA-based formulations	41
2.2.4. Experimental Biodegradation data library of mcl-PHA-based formulations construction	42
2.3. Case study for PHAs properties and processability data libraries	46
2.3.1. Processability and Products properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV) and their blends (scl/mcl-PHAs).....	47
2.3.2. Processability and Products properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs and their blends (mcl/scl-PHAs).....	52
2.3.3. Rheological Properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV), mcl-PHAs and their blends (scl/mcl-PHAs)	58
3. Conclusions	69
4. References	70
5. Annex.....	74
Overview of the Toxicity Data Libraries of scl- and mcl-based formulations.....	74
Overview of the Biodegradation Data Libraries of scl- and mcl-based formulations.	88
Overview of the Data Libraries for the Mechanical, Thermal and Rheological Properties of scl- and mcl-based formulations.	115

List of Tables

Table 1. Literature Search Queries and Results for Toxicity Studies of PHB/PHBV-based Materials.	14
Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Data Libraries of PHB/PHBV formulations.....	16
Table 3. Literature Search Queries and Results for Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Studies of mcl-PHA-based materials.....	16
Table 4. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.	17
Table 5. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).	18
Table 6. Summary of variables and data structure for the cytotoxicity of scl-PHAs dataset.	18
Table 7. Summary of Metadata Used in Cytotoxicity Data Library.....	22
Table 8. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).	22
Table 9. Summary of variables and data structure for the ecotoxicity scl-PHAs' dataset	23
Table 10. Summary of variables and data structure for the cyto/ecotoxicity mcl-PHAs' dataset. ...	27
Table 11. Literature Search Queries and Results for Biodegradation Studies of scl-PHA-based Formulations.	34
Table 12. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations.....	35
Table 13. Each of the 5 worksheets representing a different category of data for scl-PHAs biodegradation data library.	36
Table 14. Each of the 5 worksheets representing a different category of data for scl-PHAs biodegradation data library.	37
Table 15. Literature Search Queries and Results for Biodegradation Studies of mcl-PHAs materials.	41
Table 16. Overview of input (feature) and output (target) variables used to construct the mcl-PHA's biodegradation data library.	44
Table 17. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of scl-PHAs materials.	47
Table 18. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of scl-PHAs materials.	48
Table 19. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).....	48
Table 20. Overview of Input (Feature) and Output (Target) Variables Used to Construct the Materials processability and products properties data library of scl-PHAs.....	49
Table 21. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of mcl-PHAs materials.	53
Table 22. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.....	53
Table 23. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.	54

Table 24. Overview of Processability and Product Properties Data Library of mcl-PHAs Formulations.	55
Table 25. Literature Search Queries and Results for rheological properties of scl-PHAs materials..	59
Table 26. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Rheological Data Libraries of scl-PHAs.....	60
Table 27. Overview of Rheological Parameters and Datasets for scl-PHAs.....	61
Table 28. Summary of Rheological and Mechanical Parameters for scl- and mcl-PHAs.	62
Table 29. Literature Search Queries and Results for rheological properties of mcl-PHAs materials.	65
Table 30. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Rheological Data Libraries on mcl-PHAs	66
Table 31. Overview of Rheological Parameters and Datasets for mcl-PHAs.	66

List of Figures

Figure 1. ANIPH’s Predictive System Data Libraries Construction Workflow	12
Figure 2. Experimental setup for PHN biodegradation. Images showing the PHN test samples in the lake water system (top row). Laboratory-scale incubation bottles used for the biodegradation experiments in soil, compost, and lake water environments, each equipped with a 1 N KOH CO ₂ trap for monitoring mineralization under aerobic conditions at 25 °C (bottom row).	43
Figure 3. General structure of PHAs. R denotes one of the radicals shown in the table, n represents the number of repetitions of the monomer(s) (which can be arranged in tandem or randomly), and x signifies the number of CH ₂ groups within the main chain of each monomer. For the classification of PHAs, the total number of carbons present in the monomer is used, calculated as (R + x + 2). These biopolyesters can be classified based on the carbon chain length (R) of their monomers: short-chain PHAs (4–5 carbons), medium-chain PHAs (6–14 carbons), and long-chain PHAs (more than 14 carbons) (Getino et al., 2024).	46

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
scl-PHAs	Short Chain Length Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PHB	Polyhydroxybutyrate
PHBV	Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate
mcl-PHAs	Medium chain length Polyhydroxyalkanoates
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
ML	Machine Learning
PHAs	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PP	Polypropylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PE	Polyethylene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PHN	Polyhydroxynonanoate
PDI	Polydispersity Index
DFS	Dynamic frequency sweep
DTS	Dynamic temperature sweep

Executive Summary

The deliverable **D2.8, “ANIPH Data Libraries”**, forms the main data infrastructure facilitating the building up of the ANIPH Artificial Intelligence (AI) predictive tool (**D2.5**). In order to fully align with the goals of Task 2.5.1, the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) developed comprehensive, high-quality datasets encapsulating the physicochemical, processability, (eco)toxicological and biodegradability properties of short-chain length polyhydroxyalkanoates (**scl-PHAs**), e.g. polyhydroxybutyrate and polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate (PHB and PHBV), medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoates (**mcl-PHAs**) (C6-C10 homopolymers and copolymers), and their blends (**scl/mcl-PHAs**) with different additives and building blocks.

The deliverable describes the design, sources, structure, and content of the following core data libraries:

- **Physicochemical and Processability Data Libraries**
- **Biodegradation Data Library**
- **Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Data Libraries**

These databases combined experimentally observed descriptors, aligned along the principles of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse). Data was gathered with the help of systematic literature mining and processed using standardized templates suitable for AI. The resulting datasets form the basis for the AI-predictive models generated during Deliverable **D2.5**, allowing for quantitative predictions of processability, biodegradation, and toxicity of scl/mcl-PHA-based formulations.

The **D2.8** directly supports the objectives of ANIPH with reliable, accessible and interoperable data to perform safe and sustainable by design (**SSbD**) assessments, regulatory convergence and long-term traceability of the biopolymer value chain.

1. Introduction

The worldwide production of petroleum-based plastics has grown exponentially in just a few decades - from 1.5 million tons in 1950 to 359 million tons in 2018. This has led to a significant increase in plastic waste. Nowadays, over 60% of consumer plastic waste comes from households, mostly single-use food packaging composed of petroleum-based derivatives. Furthermore, in the domestic and industrial fields, the use of plastic materials exceeded their global production by up to 400 Mt/year (Bolla et al., 2025). It is widely known that the exploitation of petroleum to meet current demand for plastic materials poses serious environmental concerns, including global warming, human health risks, and ecosystem toxicity.

To address this problem, polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), a biobased, biodegradable material class, have emerged. PHAs are biosynthesized and stored by bacteria as intracellular granules that serve as carbon and energy reserves. They are formed when nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, or oxygen are limited, but carbon is abundant. The most common types are PHB and PHBV (Anjum *et al.*, 2016; Adeleye *et al.*, 2020; Sharma, Sehgal, and Gupta, 2021). PHAs can potentially replace conventional plastics in various sectors due to their physicochemical properties similar to those of petroleum-based plastics (PP, PET, PE, PVC). They can be produced from renewable feedstock, including agricultural and industrial waste, and safely biodegrade in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions.

However, PHAs have disadvantages, including high production costs, limited performance, processing challenges, and thermal instability (Li, Yang & Loh, 2016). Addressing these requires understanding key influencing factors. Reducing costs, by using low-cost or waste substrates and optimizing processes, can make PHAs more competitive with conventional plastics. Therefore, to advance the circular bioeconomy, research should prioritize generating reliable data on PHA processing and environmental impacts. Key research needs include systematic assessment of mechanical and rheological properties, biodegradability, and potential toxicity, as these factors affect both application suitability and long-term environmental outcomes. Addressing the current, scattered, and inconsistent reporting of these properties is essential to building predictive models and performing robust environmental engineering assessments. Comprehensive, standardized datasets are necessary to effectively compare materials, evaluate performance relative to conventional plastics, and determine the actual contribution of PHAs to sustainability.

Polymer informatics applies machine learning (ML) to accelerate polymer discovery and design. Progress is limited by the lack of large-scale, high-quality, open polymer datasets and standardized data collection methods. Most current databases are not openly available for ML, despite resources such as PolyInfo and the Polymer Genome. Reliable PHA data mainly comes from scientific publications and open databases, but this research is fragmented across disciplines, each using its own data formats and metrics. This results in persistent data heterogeneity, genomic sequences, rheological curves, spectroscopic results, and sustainability indicators are difficult to integrate.

Without systematic meta-analysis and standardized protocols, data loss, repetition, and limited reproducibility remain challenges.

To fill these gaps, the main research needs are: (1) creating specialized data libraries that systematically collect and organize information on PHA material properties, biodegradability, and toxicity outcomes for reliable environmental modeling and decision-making; (2) designing these libraries to be comprehensive, inclusive, and reproducible; (3) curating extensive, detailed data on physicochemical, mechanical, and rheological properties, as well as biodegradation and toxicity; (4) integrating data at multiple levels, including monomer composition, material performance, degradation behavior, and environmental fate, to provide a holistic view of PHA materials; (5) ensuring long-term usability and inclusiveness of these datasets in accordance with the FAIR principles; and (6) integrating data from diverse sources such as academic research and industrial production to fully capture the capabilities and limitations of PHAs and support robust, data-driven decision-making (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

In accordance with the European Regulation (European Parliament and Council, 2006) for Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) (European Parliament and Council, 2006), data-driven computational approaches such as Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR), Grouping and Read-Across are promoted as alternative methods to animal testing (European Chemicals Agency, 2017). While to date (Q)SARs have mostly supplemented experimental data, it is expected that they will increasingly be used to replace test data, particularly for environmental and materials-related endpoints.

Moreover, to comply with REACH, ANIPH develops predictive data libraries that minimize vertebrate testing and collect all available information on the properties of polymeric materials and their additives. These properties include physicochemical, biological, toxicological, and ecotoxicological aspects. Data from *in silico* models, such as QSAR, are integrated with experimental datasets. QSARs are mathematical models developed on the premise that molecular structures influence key endpoints, such as physicochemical properties, (eco)toxicological behavior, and environmental fate (Puzyn et al., 2018). These structures are summarized by descriptors, which are properties measured experimentally or computed theoretically. Descriptors are central in predictive modeling, linking structure to activity or performance. Reliable characterization data is essential for robust QSAR development, which is a focus of the ANIPH project.

Accordingly, **AUA** has developed highly validated predictive QSAR models. As detailed in D2.5, these use statistical and ML approaches to predict processability, biodegradation, and (eco)toxicity of **scl-** and **mcl-PHAs** formulations proposed within the ANIPH framework. For D2.8, relevant literature, including reports, tables, and graphs, was used for the endpoints of interest. This data was assembled into comprehensive, high-quality datasets to develop data-driven predictive methods, as described in **D2.5**.

The aim of D2.8 is to create a comprehensive basis for robust PHA data libraries. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate and curate existing data on the physicochemical characteristics of PHAs, including their mechanical (strength, elasticity, and hardness), thermal, and rheological properties relevant to their processing. In addition, deliverable **D2.8** aims to collect, organize, and evaluate studies on

the biodegradation behavior of PHAs across diverse environments, including soil, water, and composting systems. Furthermore, it integrates available toxicity data related to the cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity of PHAs. Thus, these libraries lay the foundation for an accessible, high-quality data infrastructure that enables innovation, informed risk assessment, and alignment with emerging sustainability and policy goals.

2. Methodology

Three types of core databases were developed under the ANIPH framework by **AUA** through a systematic literature mining and data extraction process, encompassing detailed physicochemical, processability, toxicological and biodegradability information for various formulations based on **scl-PHAs** (mainly PHB and PHBV), **mcl-PHAs** (C6–C10 homopolymers and copolymers) and their blends (**scl/mcl-PHAs**), with different additives and building blocks. These curated datasets collectively form the predictive system data libraries of ANIPH, enabling advanced ML modeling, performance prediction, and regulatory alignment in support of safe and sustainable material innovation.

A detailed workflow for the ANIPH databases' construction is depicted below in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. ANIPH's Predictive System Data Libraries Construction Workflow.

More specifically, the diagram of **Figure 1** above depicts the workflow used for the “**Task 2.5.1: Data Libraries for the ANIPH Predictive System**”, defining a systematic process for developing robust, ML-ready datasets. It started with the collection of experimental data from biodegradation in soil, compost, freshwater, and marine environments, and from cytotoxicity, ecotoxicity, and the thermal, rheological, and mechanical properties of PHA-based materials. It then followed by the mining of bibliographic and database sources, such as scientific literature on PHA, PHBV and PHN compounds, public ecotoxicity and QSAR archives, and historical project datasets. The collected information was then curated and harmonized by normalizing the units and formats, treating missing values and outliers, and confirming completeness for reliability and comparability. Finally, the curated datasets were stored in well-structured databases formatted for ML applications, ensuring interoperability, re-accessibility, and long-term reusability within the project’s predictive framework. In this deliverable we provided information on materials, performance, and all safety-related aspects. The sustainability-related aspects will be presented later in D5.3, as many sustainability metrics (e.g., LCA, environmental impacts) rely on hazard and exposure data generated during the safety assessment. Finally, under Task 2.5.1, all relevant data will be gathered into a central repository, including materials data, technical performance metrics, regulatory requirements, energy and water consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, workplace conditions (exposure levels and associated risks), consumer exposure information, as well as market, economic, societal, and ethical data.

2.1. Case study for PHAs Toxicity Data Libraries

The establishment of comprehensive eco/cytotoxicity data libraries for PHAs represents a pivotal effort toward understanding and mitigating potential biological and environmental risks associated with these emerging bioplastics. PHAs are increasingly recognized as sustainable alternatives to petrochemical plastics. However, the heterogeneity in their monomer composition, molecular weight distribution, and degradation products introduces significant uncertainty regarding their biocompatibility and ecotoxicological profiles. Currently, toxicity data for PHAs are dispersed across various studies employing inconsistent experimental protocols, endpoints, and exposure conditions, hindering comparative analysis and the development of predictive models. Therefore, the creation of curated and standardized data sets enables the systematic integration of *in vitro* and *in vivo* toxicity data relevant to PHAs.

This tool can encompass endpoints including cytotoxicity, acute and chronic ecotoxicity. The inclusion of physicochemical characteristics (e.g., monomer composition, inclusion of additives, shape etc.) alongside biological response data will facilitate the establishment of composition-toxicity relationships and improve the predictive performance of the QSAR model. Beyond supporting mechanistic understanding, this dataset will provide a scientific basis for risk assessment and regulatory evaluation of PHAs under frameworks such as REACH and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) test guidelines. By harmonizing data across experimental systems and computational tools, it will enhance reproducibility, foster data-driven material

optimization, and accelerate the safe and sustainable deployment of PHAs in biomedical, packaging, and agricultural applications.

Given the variability in the molecular structure of PHAs, toxicity can differ significantly between scl-PHAs and mcl-PHAs. For this reason, separate data libraries were created, beginning with the better-documented scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV) and extending to mcl-PHAs and their blends or additives. Although PHAs are generally considered biocompatible and non-toxic, predicting their toxicity requires careful consideration of the physicochemical and structural descriptors that influence their degradation behavior and biological interactions. Among these, chemical composition and structure of the monomer play a central role, as they determine the hydrophobicity, crystallinity of the polymer, and the nature of the degradation products. The resulting by-products are also critical, as toxicity may arise not from the polymer itself but from intermediate fragments or monomers released during environmental or biological degradation. In addition, morphology and physical characteristics, including particle or fragment size and material form (membrane, fiber, or particle), particularly affect accessibility to enzymes or cells, thereby regulating both degradation kinetics and exposure pathways. Molecular weight and the presence of copolymers or additives further influence stability and interactions with biological media.

For the cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity data library of scl-PHAs, a systematic literature review to collect the required data for the study was completed to select a variety of peer-reviewed research papers based on targeted queries focusing on physicochemical and cyto/ ecotoxicity metrics for scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV) and their blends with mcl-PHAs, with different additives and building blocks with an emphasis on the proposed additives.

Diverse scientific databases such as Scopus and PubMed were identified to search for appropriate research studies. Google Scholar was also used to broaden the search scope. After identifying the databases, the next phase involved deriving keywords to ensure relevant articles could be identified in the research. The identified keywords included "PHBV", "PHB", "polyhydroxybutyrate", "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate", "poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)", "toxic", "ecotox", "eco-toxicity", "cytotoxicity", "toxicology", "biocompatibility", and names of the requested 'green' additives of ANIPH (Table 1). Boolean operators AND/OR to facilitate quicker access to relevant articles as they define associations between keywords in a search. The operators were used to develop search phrases such as "PHBV" OR "PHB," AND "toxic" OR "ecotox" AND "lignin," OR "orotic acid," OR "castor oil".

Table 1. Literature Search Queries and Results for Toxicity Studies of PHB/PHBV-based Materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("toxicological properties" OR toxicity OR toxicology OR ecotoxicity OR "eco-toxicity" OR ecotoxicology) AND ("polyhydroxybutyrate" OR phb OR "poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR phbv OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR phn) (<i>Scopus</i>)	277 Documents

<p>TITLE-ABS-KEY ((PHBV OR PHB OR "polyhydroxybutyrate" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)") AND (toxicity OR toxicology OR ecotoxicity OR cytotoxicity OR biocompatibility) AND (lignin OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR theobromine OR fructose OR glucose OR sucrose OR lactose OR maltose OR melezitose OR dextran OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR limonene OR thymol OR starch OR "starch filler" OR sorbitol OR maltodextrin OR hydroxybenzoate OR PHN OR "polyhydroxynonanoate")) (<i>Scopus</i>)</p>	<p>104 Documents</p>
<p>TITLE-ABS-KEY ((PHBV OR PHB OR "polyhydroxybutyrate" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)") AND (toxic OR ecotox OR "eco-toxicity" OR cytotoxicity) AND (lignin OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR fructose OR glucose OR sucrose OR lactose OR maltose OR melezitose OR dextran OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR limonene OR thymol OR "starch-based fillers" OR sorbitol OR maltodextrin OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR probiotics OR antibiotics)) (<i>PubMed</i>)</p>	<p>98 Documents</p>

The third phase in data collection regarded the selection of literature. From the application of search phrases, **479** articles were identified from different scientific databases for both cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity. To select relevant studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as showcased in Table 2 below. The inclusion criteria shown emphasized studies aligned with the research topic regarding the toxicity of PHB/PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs. Studies were limited to those that utilized primary methods for data collection and only English-published articles to eliminate the need for further translation. While the exclusion of non-English articles may have led to missing important insights from major agricultural countries such as Japan and China, the inclusion of only English publications was to ensure the reach to an international audience. Furthermore, English is the standard language for international publications. The focus was on full-text studies to ensure comprehensive insights were

obtained. Duplicates and secondary studies were also removed, leading to **42** that were considered in the data library for cytotoxicity and **21** for ecotoxicity.

Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Data Libraries of PHB/PHBV formulations.

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on the cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity information on PHB/PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity information on PHB/PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

Accordingly, for the mcl-PHAs data library the same three phase research strategy was employed. The identified keywords, in this case where more suitable for this type of PHAs (C6- C10 homopolymers and copolymers) and included "PHN", "polyhydroxynonanoate", "mcl-PHAs", "cytotoxicity", "ecotoxicity", "cell viability", "LD50" or "LC50" or "Acute Toxicity" or "Subchronic Toxicity" or "Chronic Toxicity" or "MTT" or "LDH" or "Cytotoxicity Assessment" or "ecotoxicity assessment" or "Environmental toxicity".

Table 3. Literature Search Queries and Results for Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Studies of mcl-PHA-based materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA" OR "PHA blend" OR "scl-mcl blend" OR "PHN"OR"bacterial polyester" or "microbial bioplastics") AND ("cytotoxicity"or"ecotoxicity"or"cell viability" or "LD50"or"LC50"or"Acute Toxicity" or "Subchronic Toxicity" or "Chronic Toxicity" or "MTT" or "LDH" or "Cytotoxicity Assesment" or "ecotoxicity assessment" or "Environmental toxicity" or "Aquatic toxicity" or "Soil toxicity" or "Marine ecosystem impact" or	142 Documents

"Ecotoxicological evaluation" or "Toxicity to aquatic organisms" or "Daphnia magna toxicity" or "Sediment toxicity" or "Cytotoxicity assay" or "Apoptosis induction" or "in vitro toxicity" or "in vivo toxicity" or "Biocompatibility" or "IC50")) (Scopus)	
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA" OR "PHA blend" OR "scl-mcl blend" OR "PHN"OR"bacterial polyester") AND ("cytotoxicity"or"ecotoxicity"or"cell viability"or"LD50"or"LC50") or"Acute Toxicity"or"Subchronic Toxicity"or"Chronic Toxicity"or"MTT"or"LDH"or"Cytotoxicity Assesment") (Scopus)	68 Documents

The third phase in data collection regarded the selection of literature. From the application of search phrases, **210** articles were identified from different scientific databases for both cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity. To select relevant studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as showcased in Table 4 below. The inclusion criteria shown emphasized studies aligned with the research topic regarding the toxicity of mcl-PHAs, with or without additives. Studies were limited to those that utilized primary methods for data collection and only English-published articles to eliminate the need for further translation. The main focus was on full-text studies to ensure comprehensive insights were obtained. Duplicates and secondary studies were also removed, leading to **13** that were considered in the data library for cytotoxicity and **1** for ecotoxicity.

Table 4. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Cytotoxicity and Ecotoxicity Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on the cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity information on mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with PHB/PHBV	Studies not focused on cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity information on mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with PHB/PHBV.

Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

2.1.1. Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV formulations)

A data curation process was performed on these **42** most relevant research articles, concluding in the development of a cytotoxicity database specific to PHB/PHBV formulations and their blends with mcl-PHAs. The extracted data were systematically compiled into a database constructed within a Microsoft Excel environment, comprising 5 distinct worksheets.

Table 5. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).

Worksheets	Parameters
Worksheet_1_Material Properties	Polymer type, Percentage of the monomer Hydroxybutyrate (PHB), Percentage of the monomer Hydroxyvalerate (PHV), Additive Name and Percentage, Average molecular weight (Mw). Shape/Form, Measurements, Additive presence, Respective additive concentrations
Worksheet_2_Cytotoxicity Experimental Parameters	Standards used for cytotoxicity, Assay, Cell line, Cell_line_type, Number of Cells Direct/Indirect Contact, Concentration tested Dilutions, Temperature of incubation etc.
Worksheet_3_Cytotoxicity Outputs	Cell Viability, IC50 etc.
Worksheet_4_Metadata	Authors, year of publication, title of the research paper, DOI
Worksheet_5_Info	Abbreviations used within the database

A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations and useful information contained in the dataset. Each of the worksheets corresponded to a specific data category and organized as follows:

Table 6. Summary of variables and data structure for the cytotoxicity of scl-PHAs dataset.

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	Categorical

Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	Categorical
Monomer A	Primary monomer	None	varies	Categorical
Monomer B	Primary monomer	None	varies	Categorical
HB_ratio	Hydroxybutyrate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
HV_ratio	Hydroxyvalerate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
Molecular_weight (Mw)	Weight-average molar mass	g/mol	7300-6800000	Numerical
Molecular_weight (Mn)	Number-average molar mass	kDa, g/mol	86-450000	Numerical
Polydispersity_Index (PDI)	Polydispersity index	ratio	1-10	Numerical
Shape	Shape/morphology (film, particle, ribbon, etc.)	None	varies	Categorical
Dimensions	Dimensions of sample	mm, cm, μ m	0,01-400	Numerical
Additives	Presence of incorporated additives	None	Yes/No	Categorical
Additive_name	Name of incorporated additives	None	varies	Categorical
Additive_Percentage	Additive content	%	0-100	Numerical
ISO	ISO standard used for cytotoxicity testing	None	varies	Categorical
ASTM	ASTM standard used for cytotoxicity testing	None	varies	Categorical
Assay	Type of cytotoxicity assay performed	None	varies	Categorical

Cell_Line	Name of the cell line used in the assay	None	varies	Categorical
Cell_Line_Type	Classification of the cell line (e.g. fibroblast, epithelial)	None	varies	Categorical
Exposure_Type	Method of sample exposure to cells	None	Direct/Indirect	Categorical
Number_of_Cells_per_well, Inoculum_concentration_units	Cell density used in each well of the assay plate	cells/well	2000-20000	Numerical
Culture_Medium	Medium used to culture the cells	None	varies	Categorical
Dilution_Medium	Medium used for sample dilution	None	varies	Categorical
Concentration, Concentration_Units	Concentration of the test sample applied	mg/L, mg/mL, µg/mL, µM	0-2500	Numerical
Dilution	Dilution factor or ratio of the test sample before exposure	Ratio	0-1000	Numerical
Incubation_Time, Incubation_Time_Units	Duration of cell exposure to the test sample	hours	18-336	Numerical
Incubation_Temperature, Incubation_Temperature_Units	Temperature at which incubation was conducted	°C	37	Numerical
CO ₂ _Percentage	Percentage of CO ₂ used during incubation	%	5	Numerical

Air	Atmospheric conditions during incubation	None	Humidified	Categorical
Extraction_Time, Extraction_Time_Units	Duration of the extraction process	hours	24-72	Numerical
Extraction_Temperature, Extraction_Temperature_Units	Temperature at which extraction was performed	°C	37	Numerical
Extraction_Medium	Medium used for extraction of leachables	None	varies	Categorical
Extraction_Surface_Area, Extraction_Surface_Area_Units	Ratio of material surface area to extraction medium volume	cm ² /mL	0,5-1,25	Numerical
Number_of_cells_well	Number of viable cells remaining after exposure	cells/well	300-23000	Numerical
Cell_viability_percentage	Percentage of viable cells after exposure	%	13-158	Numerical
Toxicity	Qualitative measure of cytotoxic effect based on a 70% cell viability threshold	None	Toxic/Non toxic	Categorical
Growth_constant_μ, Growth_constant_μ_Units	Specific growth rate constant	h ⁻¹	0-2	Numerical
Relative_Growth_Rate	Growth rate relative to control	%	0-200	Numerical
Toxicity_Grade	Numerical classification of toxicity	None	0-4	Numerical

	intensity (e.g. 0 = non-toxic, 4 = severe)			
Growth_Inhibition_Percentage	Percentage of growth inhibition relative to control	%	0-100	Numerical

Table 7. Summary of Metadata Used in Cytotoxicity Data Library.

Feature	Description
Study_id	Unique identifier assigned to each study entry
Author	Name(s) of the author(s) of the study
Date	Publication date
Title	Title of the publication or study
Doi	Digital Object Identifier for the referenced study

2.1.2. Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV formulations)

The most relevant research articles (21 studies) for the curation of the ecotoxicity database were used. Following the structural framework of the Ecotox database (ECOTOX | Home), the curated information included data on the ecotoxicological effects of the polymers studied at organism, population, and ecosystem levels. As in the case of cytotoxicity, this information was systematically organized into 5 Microsoft Excel worksheets.

Table 8. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).

Worksheets	Parameters
Worksheet_1_Polymer_Info	Polymer type, Percentage of the monomer Hydroxybutyrate (PHB), Percentage of the monomer Hydroxyvalerate (PHV), Additive Name and Percentage, Average molecular weight (Mw). Shape/Form, Measurements, Additive presence, Respective additive concentrations
Worksheet_2_Ecotoxicity Experimental Inputs	Species_name and Species_group (terrestrial plant, air-breathing animal, aquatic)

	organisms), Environmental medium, Exposure type, Observation period, Exposure Concentration, Test location, Toxicity (Acute or Chronic)
Worksheet_3_Ecotoxicity Outputs	Mortality rates (LC50, LD50), Sub-lethal effects, (EC50, NOEC, LOEC), Toxicity Grade, Toxicity classification (according to GHS)
Worksheet_4_Metadata	Authors, year of publication, title of the research paper, DOI
Worksheets_5_Info	Abbreviations used within the database

A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations contained in the dataset.

Table 9. Summary of variables and data structure for the ecotoxicity scl-PHAs' dataset.

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	Categorical
Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	Categorical
Monomer_A	Primary monomer	None	varies	Categorical
Monomer_B	Primary monomer	None	varies	Categorical
HB_ratio	Hydroxybutyrate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
HV_ratio	Hydroxyvalerate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
Molecular_Weight (Mw)	Weight-average molar mass	g/molL	163000-350200	Numerical
Molecular_Weight (Mn)	Number-average molar mass	g/mol	7800-300000	Numerical
Polydispersity_Index (PDI)	Polydispersity index	ratio	1-10	Numerical
Shape	Shape/morphology (film, particle, ribbon, etc.)	None	Varies	Categorical
Dimensions	Dimensions of sample	mm, cm, μ m	0,01-400	Numerical
Additives	Presence of incorporated additives	None	Limited	Categorical

Additive_Name	Name of incorporated additives	None	varies	Categorical
Additive_Percentage	Additive content	%	0-100	Numerical
Additive_Use	Type of additive (e.g. filler, plasticizer)	None	varies	Categorical
Polymer_Percentage	PHA content in final formulation	%	0-100	Numerical
Species_Name	Scientific name of the test organism	None	varies	Categorical
Species_Group	Taxonomic or functional group of the organism	None	Limited	Categorical
Initial_Organism_Age, Initial_Organism_Units	Age of the organism at the start of exposure	Days, weeks, months, g, μ m	0-220	Numerical
Exposure_Type	Type of exposure applied during the test	None	Limited	Categorical
Media_Type	Type of test medium used (e.g., water, sediment, soil)	None	Limited	Categorical
Test_Location	Location or facility where the test was conducted	None	varies	Categorical
Tested_Concentration, Tested_Concentration_Units	Nominal or measured concentration of the tested substance	g/g, g/Kg, g/L, mg/Kg, mg/kg/day, mg/L, mL/L, μ g/mL	0-2000	Numerical
Observation_Period, Observation_Period_Units	Duration of the exposure or observation phase	Minutes, Hours, days, weeks	2-183	Numerical
Toxicity	Indicates whether the test represents acute or chronic toxicity	None	Limited	Categorical

EC10, EC10 Units	Concentration of the substance causing 10% effect on the test population	mg/L	0-1600	Numerical
EC50, EC50 Units	Concentration of the substance causing 50% effect on the test population	mg/L	0-4000	Numerical
Toxic_Units	Unit expressing toxicity level based on standard formula (e.g., 100/EC50)	None	0-14	Numerical
LC50, LC50_Units	Concentration of the substance lethal to 50% of the test organism	mg/L	0-100	Numerical
LD_50, LD_50 Units	Dose of the substance lethal to 50% of the test organisms	mg/kg	0-2000	Numerical
Mortality_Percentage	Percentage of organisms that died during the exposure period	%	0-100	Numerical
Body_Mass_Change_Percentage	Percentage of organisms that changed in body mass compared to control	%	0-100	Numerical
Size_Increase, Size_Increase Units	Change in organism size during exposure	g, μ m	0-300	Numerical
Number_Of_Juveniles	Total number of juveniles produced per test unit	None	0-8	Numerical
Number_Of_Cocoons	Total number of cocoons produced during the test	None	0-4	Numerical
SGI_Percentage	Seed Germination	%	0-100	Numerical

	Index as a percentage of control			
Survival_Rate_Percentage	Percentage of organisms that survived exposure	%	0-100	Numerical
Normal_Plutei_Percentage	Percentage of organisms that survived exposure	%	0-100	Numerical
Specific_Growth_Rate, Specific_Growth_Rate_Units	Measure of how fast an organism (or population algae, fish, and daphnia) grows over time	%/day	0-100	Numerical
Weight_Gain, Weight_Gain_Units	Increase in organism weight measured over time compared to control	%, g	0-200	Numerical
Plant_Height, Plant_Heights_Units	Average height of plants measured at test termination	cm	0-50	Numerical
Shoot_Biomass, Shoot_Biomass_Units	Dry or fresh weight of the shoot biomass	mg, g	0-80	Numerical
Foliar_C_N_ratio	Ratio of carbon to nitrogen in plant foliage	None	0-74	Numerical
Plant_Growth	Overall plant growth rate during exposure	%	0-100	Numerical
Toxicity_Grade	Numerical value indicating the severity or intensity of toxicity effects	None	0-2	Numerical
Toxicity_Classification	Classification of the substance's toxicity according to GHS criteria	None	Limited	Categorical

2.1.3. Cyto/Ecotoxicity Data Library of mcl-PHA-based formulations

The available literature for cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity of **mcl-PHAs** was very limited. However, the **13** most relevant research articles were identified and utilized to develop the cytotoxicity database that focuses on mcl-PHAs, both with and without additives. One research study was included in the database regarding ecotoxicity. The extracted data were systematically compiled into a structured database using Microsoft Excel environment, using the same organizational framework as the cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity databases previously developed for scl-PHAs (e.g. Sections 2.1.1, 2.1.2). The database consisted of 8 distinct worksheets, each corresponding to a specific data category and organized as follows:

1. *Material Properties (e.g. Physicochemical Information)*
2. *Cytotoxicity experimental parameters (inputs)*
3. *Cytotoxicity Endpoints (outputs)*
4. *Ecotoxicity experimental parameters (inputs)*
5. *Ecotoxicity Endpoints (outputs)*
6. *Overall Toxicity, (the results from both cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity assays are integrated to generate a single unified endpoint, expressed as toxic or non-toxic).*
7. *Metadata*
8. *Info*

Table 10. Summary of variables and data structure for the cyto/ecotoxicity mcl-PHAs' dataset.

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	Categorical
Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	Categorical
Initial_scl_PHA_ratio	Initial short chain length PHA ratio (3-5 atoms of C)	mol%	0-100	Numerical
Initial_3HB_ratio	Initial 3-hydroxybutyrate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
Initial_mcl_PHA_ratio	Initial medium chain length PHA ratio (6-14 atoms of C)	mol%	0-100	Numerical
3HHx ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyhexanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical

3HHp ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyheptanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
3HO ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyoctanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
3HN ratio	Initial 3-hydroxynonanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
3HD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxydecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
3HDD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxydodecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	Numerical
Molecular Weight (Mw)	Weight-average molar mass	g/mol	23900-4400000	Numerical
Molecular Weight (Mn)	Number-average molar mass	g/mol	35575-2101000	Numerical
Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Polydispersity Index	ratio	1,06-7	Numerical
Additive	Presence of Incorporated additives	None	Limited	Categorical
Additive Name	Name of incorporated additives	None	varies	Categorical
Additive Percentage	Additive Content	%	0-100	Numerical
Additive_Type	Type of additive (e.g. filler, plasticizer)	None	varies	Categorical
final_PHA_percentage	PHA content in final formulation	%	0-100	Numerical
final_formulation_Mw	Weight-average molar	g/mol		Numerical

	mass in final formulation			
Final_formulation_Mn	Number-average molar mass in final formulation	g/mol		Numerical
Final_formulation_PDI	Polydispersity Index (PDI) of final formulation	ratio		Numerical

The complete curated raw data libraries on scl- and mcl-PHAs cyto- and eco-toxicity, including all input and output variables, have been uploaded to the [AUA Zenodo repository](#).

2.2. Case study for PHAs Biodegradation Data Libraries

Biodegradation is affected by multiple factors such as environment conditions (i.e. temperature, moisture etc.), the polymer composition, molecular weight, crystallinity, chemical structure, reduction potential, hydrophilicity, breakdown products, but the extent of the effects from some of these factors remains unclear (Boopathy, 2000). Biodegradation is influenced by the susceptibility of the polymer carbon backbone to microbial attack (Jayasekara et al., 2005).

Research on soil biodegradation can be divided into two categories, those that indicate the degree of biodegradation, and those that indicate the mass loss over the duration of the study. The latter is more prevalent in the literature due to its ease, however, based on the ASTM standards, it is not enough to determine the degree of biodegradability of polymers by itself. Furthermore, it is the duration of soil biodegradation that makes complete studies following ASTM standards incredibly rare.

The biodegradation efficiency of PHAs is closely linked to the physical and chemical characteristics of the polymer. Degradation rates depend on the: (i) crystallinity; (ii) copolymers; and (iii) copolymeric structure. In PHBV, the 3-hydroxyvalerate insertion has a larger amorphous region, which is more vulnerable to enzymatic attack, due to the easier water penetration, absorption, and sensitivity of the isodimorphic crystalline region to the catalytic region of the enzyme. Therefore, biodegradation varies depending on the crystallinity induced by the processing method. Furthermore, based on the copolymer ratio, the amorphous region can be modified and the enzymatic activity of the depolymerase can be maximized. Copolymers are known to biodegrade faster than homopolymers due to the presence of the inherited amorphous region. For example, PHBV is formed by addition of HV to PHB, where the relative fractions of HB and HV define modulating crystallinity. This lower crystallinity of the copolymer is directly related to higher enzyme activity measured by the weight loss of PHBV. This correlation is reflected in the extent of degradation under both anaerobic and aerobic conditions. In the example of PHBV, at 3% HV content, there is no difference between the degradation of PHB and PHBV, as their crystallinity is similar. As the HV content increases, the crystallinity decreases and the biodegradation rate improves. Research shows that a HV content of around 40-50% produces the fastest biodegradation rates in soil (Arcos-Hernández et al., 2012), compost (Weng et al., 2011), and seawater (Doi et al., 1992). This result is also reflected in anaerobic environments.

PHAs powder form possesses the highest surface area to volume ratio, resulting in fastest biodegradation. It is expected that thin films benefit from increased biodegradation rates, due to the ease of moisture permeation and maximized surface area, leading to an improvement in their biodegradation rate, as their thickness decreases. Biodegradation of PHA pellets is typically slower than that of films, to a certain degree depending on the type of PHA. Consequently, when comparing biodegradations studies, it is crucial to take into account the morphology of the samples. However,

the comparisons become difficult as only a limited number of completed studies followed ASTM standards (Meereboer et al., 2020).

The inclusion of other chemical additives or blends influences PHA biodegradation on both chemical and physical levels by impeding enzymatic degradation. Non-biodegradable co-polyesters and chemicals reduce the surface area for interaction between enzymes and biodegradable polymers. Chain extenders and anti-fouling agents are among the most frequently applied chemical alterations on polymers. Consequently, they are indicated to impact biodegradation at various degrees, by hindering the activity of extracellular enzymes or by limiting the microorganisms' ability to produce the enzymes.

Research on the biodegradation of PHA blends is infrequent in many natural environments (i.e. soil and marine environments) because few other bio-based polymers, like PLA, demonstrate evidence of biodegradation. Two primary pathways of PHA blends have been investigated, plasticized PHA and PHA/PLA blends, owing to their bio-based origins and possible uses. PHA/PLA blends lower the crystallinity and are expected to enhance the biodegradation of PHA elements (Meereboer et al., 2020).

Research on the biodegradation of PHAs in soil has shown that PHAs are regarded as the most viable biodegradable substances in soil, achieving 100% biodegradation within 90 days. According to the literature, there is no established standard that specifies a (%) biodegradation threshold for polymers, to determine if they are biodegradable or merely exhibit biodegradable characteristics. The current OK Soil degradable certification specifies that it needs to achieve 90% biodegradation, either absolutely or relatively to the reference sample, within 2 years according to the ASTM 5988, through few studies have lasted that long (Vinçotte, 2012). The moisture content is linked to the enzymatic hydrolysis of PHAs to effectively hydrolyse the ester bonds, making high moisture levels enhance PHA enzymatic and biodegradation efficiency. The ideal pH for the prevalent enzymes involved in PHB degradation ranges from 6 to 9, though this can vary among different types. For typical use, soil biodegradation should finish at 20–28 °C, although it is more effective at higher temperatures (Meereboer et al., 2020).

Biodegradation studies of PHAs in marine environments have revealed that the pH of freshwater tends to be lower than that of marine water, which hinders PHA biodegradation (Federle et al., 2002). The ideal degradation temperature for PHB in freshwater (data for other PHAs is lacking) is noted to be 30 °C, which results in a degradation rate that is twice as fast as at 20 °C. However, a water temperature of 40 °C did not increase PHB degradation rates any further. PHB and PHBV biodegrade at varying rates in the aquatic environment, exhibiting a rate that is 6 time quicker in seawater compared to freshwater ponds or canals (Mergaert et al., 1992). In optimal conditions, PHA can be completely degraded within 28 days in both fresh and saltwater rivers, lakes, or oceans. PHB and PHBV (8–12% HV) biodegrade over 90% in 100 days compared to the glucose reference, meeting some of the OK marine biodegradable criteria (Vinçotte, 2019). Consequently, PHAs are

marine biodegradable as per ASTM D6691 (ASTM International, 2017) in suitable environments, yet physical degradation still needs evaluation.

PHA-based biocomposites that incorporate natural fillers can lower costs and enhance the biodegradation of PHAs, increasing water diffusion rates and optimizing water uptake (Badia et al., 2014). The inclusion of various types of fibers generally enhances biodegradation. Starch is the most effective fiber to enhance PHA biodegradation because of its hydrophilic nature, amorphous structure, and simplicity of biodegradation in both soil and marine environments. Even with the advantageous hydrophilic characteristics of natural fibres, which render them more compatible with polar biopolymers, compatibilizers are often necessary to improve the shear stress between fibre and matrix (Meereboer et al., 2020).

2.2.1. Biodegradation Data Library of PHA-based formulations

The biodegradation data library serves as a fundamental part of the ANIPH predictive framework, offering the basis for data-driven modelling and assessment of the environmental fate of PHAs and their formulations. This case study demonstrates the systematic methodology adopted for the collection, curation, and structuring of biodegradation-related data within the ANIPH framework, focusing on scl (PHBV)- and mcl (PHN)-based formulations that incorporate the project's suggested 'green' additives.

Data collection was the first stage of the PHAs' biodegradation data library construction. The quality of the data was critical to the overall case study. Data was gathered through a comprehensive literature mining process that included peer-reviewed research articles, thesis and experimental studies related to PHA degradation across different environmental conditions. The selected studies investigated the degradation behavior of materials in soil, freshwater, and marine environments, considering both controlled laboratory and real-field conditions. The focus was placed on identifying studies reporting quantitative degradation metrics, such as mass loss, CO₂ evolution, alongside associated environmental and physicochemical parameters (structural, morphological, thermal, mechanical, rheological properties, etc).

Data obtained through these sources generally had a higher degree of credibility and accuracy because they were obtained directly from laboratory experiments. However, rich data were contained in articles and collecting them required much effort and was mainly done manually. All the available published data, such as numeric data, including polymer names and property values, were stored in tabular format (Excel files) for ease of transfer and utilization. Some of the property data were drawn out and hand-curated from graphs and digitized tables of the available studies and supplementary materials. Images and graphs were quickly converted into numerical data using the professional Plotdigitizer version 3 software (Plotdigitizer, n.d.).

The dataset for PHBV integrates information from 24 peer-reviewed publications focusing on PHBV homopolymers and copolymers formulated with various proposed additives. The dataset for PHN integrates information from biodegradation experiments that were conducted in AUA facilities.

under controlled laboratory conditions to evaluate the mineralization of PHN material in three different environments: soil, lake water and compost, under aerobic conditions at 25 °C.

Following data collection, structured databases were created in a spreadsheet format (Microsoft Excel), organized into the following interlinked worksheets that illustrate the complex aspects of biodegradation processes for PHAs:

1. Material Properties – Include composition, molecular weight distribution (Mw and Mn), crystallinity indices (Xc), additive type and concentration, and formulation details.
2. Thermal and Mechanical Properties – Contain glass transition (Tg), crystallization (Tc), melting (Tm), decomposition (Td5%) temperatures, etc, as well as tensile strength, Young's modulus, elongation at break, etc, both pre- and post-degradation.
3. Environmental Parameters – Capture experimental conditions such as temperature, pH, moisture level, oxygen availability, microbial activity, etc.
4. Degradation Metrics – Encompass quantitative endpoints including mass loss, CO₂ evolution, and time-dependent changes in thermal and mechanical performance.
5. Metadata – Record bibliographic and contextual information, such as publication title, DOI, experimental notes and abbreviations (info), ensuring traceability and reproducibility.

These well-structured biodegradation databases were designed to serve as input for supervised ML models, that are analytically presented in D2.5 “ANIPH AI Predictive tool”, predicting degradation percentages over time. To accomplish this, the data were organized to explicitly define input (feature)–output (target) relationships:

- Input variables (features) consist of molecular, physicochemical, and environmental descriptors such as monomer composition (%HB, %HV, %HN), additive concentration, Mw, Mn, Xc, Tg, Tm and Td5% temperatures, environmental pH, temperature, oxygen availability, microbial activity indices, etc.
- Target variables correspond to degradation performance metrics, including time-dependent degradation (%) derived through regression analysis of reported time-series data.

All datasets went through an extensive harmonization process to ensure consistency across studies and completeness of metadata. Units of measurements were converted to SI standards, terminology was aligned in accordance with ISO 472 polymer definitions (ISO 472:2013, International Organization for Standardization, 2013), and redundant entries were consolidated through duplicate identification based on DOI. The harmonized datasets comply with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), allowing future integration into the ANIPH ICT platform and compatibility with external databases.

Currently, the biodegradation databases include high-quality studies obtained from literature on PHBV-based formulations, as well as internal experimental work on PHN material carried out in the biodegradation lab at AUA. Looking ahead to the next phase of the project, this resource will be further extended to include experimental data from physical experiments (inputs from WP3, WP4, WP5, WP8, WP9, WP10) generated by ANIPH project partners, with particular emphasis on

degradation of mcl-PHA formulations and PHBV/mcl-PHA blends with proposed additives, in different environments with physicochemical characterizations before and after degradation. These forthcoming datasets can then be used to validate and enhance ML models generated in Deliverable D2.5, filling the gap between predictive modeling and experimental verification. Ultimately, the biodegradation databases offer a sustainable approach to linking environmental outcomes with material properties, with important SSbD (Abbate et al., 2024) contributions in ANIPH and beyond.

2.2.2. Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations

For the biodegradation database construction of **scl-PHAs**, PHBV-based formulations, a variety of peer-reviewed research papers were selected based on targeted queries shown in Table 11, focusing on the physicochemical and environmental properties, degradation metrics, thermal and mechanical characteristics of the materials, with special emphasis on the proposed additives, before and after degradation, in soil and marine in controlled and real environments.

Scopus, the well-established scientific database was identified to search for appropriate research studies. Google Scholar was also used to broaden the search scope. After identifying the databases, the next phase involved deriving keywords to ensure relevant articles could be identified in the research. The identified keywords included "PHBV", "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate", "poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)", "biodegradation", "decomposition", "microbial degradation", "mineralization", and names of the requested 'green' additives of ANIPH. Boolean operators AND/OR facilitate quicker access to relevant articles as they define associations between keywords in a search. The operators were used to develop search phrases such as "PHBV", AND "biodegradation" OR "mineralization" AND "lignin," OR "orotic acid," OR "castor oil".

Table 11. Literature Search Queries and Results for Biodegradation Studies of scl-PHA-based Formulations.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("PHBV" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "PHB" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate") AND ("biodegradation" OR "decomposition" OR "microbial degradation" OR "mineralization") AND ("lignin" OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR "fructose" OR "glucose" OR "sucrose" OR "lactose" OR "maltose" OR "melezitose" OR "dextran" OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "lignins" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR "limonene" OR "thymol" OR "starch-based fillers" OR "sorbitol" OR "maltodextrin" OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "PHN" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxynonanoate)"))	200

The above search query included **keywords** related to:

1. The term TITLE-ABS-KEY, which refers to a search field that allows you to search for specific keywords or phrases in the Title, Abstract, and Keywords of articles,
2. the copolymer PHBV, which is the biodegradable polymer being studied,

3. the requested additive to be used with the copolymer PHBV.

Using this query in the advanced search of Scopus, 200 results were found for studies from 1989 to March 2025 that met these search criteria. After identifying the studies that met the search criteria, a detailed examination of each study was followed. In order to select relevant studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as shown in Table 12 below. The inclusion criteria shown emphasized studies aligned with the research topic regarding the biodegradation of PHB(V) formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs. Studies were limited to those that utilized primary methods for data collection and only English-published articles to eliminate the need for further translation. While the exclusion of non-English articles may have led to missing important insights from major agricultural countries such as Japan and China, the inclusion of only English publications was to ensure the reach to an international audience. Furthermore, English is the standard language for international publications. The focus was on full-text studies to ensure that comprehensive insights were obtained. Duplicates and secondary studies were also removed, leading to 24 that were considered in the data library for biodegradation of scl-PHAs.

Table 12. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations.

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of data libraries focused on the biodegradation information on PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on biodegradation information on PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

We have successfully curated the **24** most relevant research papers for data collection from reported texts, graphs and tables. The data from the examined studies were entered into a database that was created in an Excel environment and included 5 worksheets. Each worksheet represented a different category of data, which was organized as follows in Table 13:

Table 13. Each of the 5 worksheets representing a different category of data for scl-PHAs biodegradation data library.

Worksheets	Parameters
Worksheet_1_Physicochemical properties	Composition details, Molecular weight distributions (Mw and Mn), Crystallinity indices, Additive presence, Respective additive concentrations, etc.
Worksheet_2_Thermal properties	glass transition temperature (Tg), crystallization temperature (Tc), melting temperature (Tm), decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss (Td5%), degradation temperature (Tdeg), heat of melting fusion (ΔH_m), heat of crystallization fusion (ΔH_c), crystallinity index (Xc), etc.
Worksheet_3_Mechanical properties	young modulus, tensile modulus, tensile strength, stress at break, yield strength, elongation at break etc.
Worksheet_4_Environmental Parameters	Temperature, pH, Moisture levels, Oxygen availability, Microbial activity, etc.
Worksheets_5(a-d) Degradation Metrics	mass loss percentages, mass loss time points, Degradation time points, Degradation percentages, Temporal changes in mechanical and thermal properties.

Table 14 below provides a detailed overview of all input (feature) and output (target) variables used to construct the scl-PHA's biodegradation data library. Each presented variable is described in terms of its definition, measurement unit, value range, and type (categorical or numerical). The complete curated raw data library on PHBV biodegradation, including all variables across the five categories, has been uploaded to the [AUA Zenodo repository](#). In Annex (Tables A8-13), an overview of the uploaded data library is presented.

Table 14. Each of the 5 worksheets representing a different category of data for scl-PHAs biodegradation data library.

Feature_Name	Description	Unit	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	categorical
Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	categorical
Sample_name	Name or code of material sample	None	varies	categorical
Sample_ratio	Component ratio (wt/wt)	ratio, %	0-100	numerical
MonomerA, MonomerB	Primary monomers	None	varies	categorical
Adjusted_HB_ratio	Hydroxybutyrate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
Adjusted_HV_ratio	Hydroxyvalerate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
Additive_1_name, Additive_2_name, Additive_3_name	Name of incorporated additives	None	varies	categorical
Additives	Presence of incorporated additives	None	Yes/No	categorical
Additive_1_type, Additive_2_type, Additive_3_type	Type of additive (e.g. filler, plasticizer)	None	varies	categorical
Additive_1_percentage, Additive_2_percentage, Additive_3_percentage	Additive content	%	0-100	numerical
PHBV _weight_percentage_final _formulation	PHBV content in final formulation	%	0-100	numerical
Viscocimetric_molar_mass	Molar mass by viscosity	g/mol	100-170	numerical
Soil_burial_time_for_Mv, Soil_burial_time_for_Mw, Soil_burial_time_for_Mn, Soil_burial_time_for_PDI, Soil_burial_time_for_mois ture_content	Soil burial time before test	months	0-12	numerical
Mw	Weight-average molar mass	kDa	290-700	numerical

Relative_Mw	Relative molecular weight	%	29-100	numerical
Incubation_time_for_relative_Mw	Incubation period for relative Mw	days	1-27	numerical
Mn	Number-average molar mass	kDa	111-350	numerical
PDI	Polydispersity index	ratio	2,2-2,9	numerical
Moisture_content_formulations	Moisture in the formulation	%	0-19	numerical
Density	Density of sample	g/cm ³	0,7-1,6	numerical
Density_units	Units for density	g/cm ³ , kg/m ³	-	categorical
Void_content	Void content in sample	%	0-5	numerical
Thickness_swelling	Thickness swelling after immersion	%	0-7	numerical
Sample_shape/Morphology	Shape/morphology (film, particle, ribbon, etc.)	None	varies	categorical
Dimensions	Dimensions of sample	mm, cm, µm	0,01-800	numerical
Size_units	Units for all size fields	mm, cm, µm	-	categorical
Permeability_water_vapor	Water vapor permeability	10 ⁻¹³ mol·m/(m ² ·s·Pa)	4-22	numerical
Water_absorption_capacity	Water uptake capacity	%	1-40	numerical
Film_solubility	Solubility of film	%	0-20	numerical
PHBV_crystallinity	PHBV crystalline fraction	%	52,0 – 55,9	numerical
Static_water_contact_angle	Hydrophilicity (contact angle)	degree	49-83	numerical
Biodegradation_time	Duration of biodegradation test	days	0-400	numerical
Weight loss/mass loss_percentage (Dependent Target value)	Lost mass due to biodegradation	%	0-100	numerical

Biodegradation_percentage (Dependent Target value)	Biodegradation achieved	%	0-100	numerical
Morphology	Form of specimen (matrix, fiber, etc.)	None	varies	categorical
Specimens_shape	Shape (e.g., dumbbell, bar)	None	varies	categorical
ISO, ASTM	Test standard followed	None	varies	categorical
Tmech, Tmech_units	Temperature for mechanical test	°C	20 to 190	numerical
Young_modulus	Young's modulus	MPa, Gpa	1-190	numerical
Young_modulus_units	Units for Young's modulus	MPa, GPa	-	categorical
Tensile_strength	Tensile strength	MPa, kgf/mm ² , %	0,8-190	numerical
Tensile_strength_units	Units for tensile strength	MPa, kgf/mm ²	-	categorical
Tensile_modulus	Tensile modulus	MPa, GPa	2,3-47	numerical
Tensile_modulus_units	Units for tensile modulus	MPa, GPa	-	categorical
Flexural_strength	Flexural strength	MPa	26-77	numerical
Flexural_modulus	Flexural modulus	GPa	2,3-6,5	numerical
Stress_at_break	Stress at break	GPa, MPa	0,01-36	numerical
Stress_at_break_units	Units for break stress	GPa, MPa	-	categorical
Elongation_at_break	% elongation at break	%	0-140	numerical
Yield_strength	Yield strength	MPa	12-26	numerical
Elongation_to_yield	% elongation to yield	%	0-7	numerical
Charpys_impact_energy	Impact energy (Charpy)	kJ/m ²	3,6-4,4	numerical
Impact_strength	Impact strength	kgf/mm ²	3,4-8,3	numerical
Impact_strength_units	Units for impact strength	J/m ³ , kJ/m ²	-	categorical
Impact_resistance	Impact resistance	J/m	13,5-555	numerical

2.2.3. Biodegradation Data Library of mcl-PHA-based formulations

Accordingly, for the **mcl-PHAs** biodegradation data library the same research strategy was employed in Scopus well-established database with targeted Queries (Table 15). The identified keywords, in this case where more suitable for medium-chain-length PHAs (C6-C10 homopolymers and copolymers) and included "PHN", "polyhydroxynonanoate", "mcl-PHAs", "biodegradation", "decomposition", "microbial degradation", "mineralization" and names of the requested 'green' additives of ANIPH. Boolean operators AND/OR facilitate quicker access to relevant articles as they define associations between keywords in a search. The operators were used to develop search phrases such as "PHBV", AND "biodegradation" OR "mineralization " AND "lignin", OR "orotic acid ", OR "castor oil".

Table 15. Literature Search Queries and Results for Biodegradation Studies of mcl-PHAs materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA") AND ("biodegradation" OR "decomposition" OR "microbial degradation" OR "mineralization"))	75
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA") AND ("biodegradation" OR "decomposition" OR "microbial degradation" OR "mineralization") AND ("lignin" OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR "fructose" OR "glucose" OR "sucrose" OR "lactose" OR "maltose" OR "melezitose" OR "dextran" OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "lignins" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR "limonene" OR "thymol" OR "starch-based fillers" OR "sorbitol" OR "maltodextrin" OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "PHN" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxynonanoate)"))	15

The above search query included **keywords** related to:

1. The term TITLE-ABS-KEY, which refers to a search field that allows you to search for specific keywords or phrases in the Title, Abstract, and Keywords of articles,
2. mcl-PHAs (C6-C10 homopolymers and copolymers), which are the biodegradable polymers being studied,
3. the requested additive to be used with the mcl-PHAs.

Using the second most targeted query of the Table 15 in the advanced search of Scopus, 15 results were found for studies from 2002 to March 2025 that met these search criteria.

After identifying the studies that met the search criteria, a detailed examination of each study was followed. There was limited literature about mcl-PHAs (C6-C10) regarding biodegradation in soil and marine (controlled and real environments) without or with the proposed additives. Among the 15 studies selected through targeted queries, only 5 addressed controlled biodegradation in soil or marine conditions which were insufficient for developing a comprehensive dataset, due to the lack of uniformity in the data that had been gathered. A large degree of variation had been observed in the experimental parameters (such as temperature, pH, microbial population, and composition of soil/seawater media), in the methods of analysis (like CO₂ evolution, weight loss, reduction in molecular weight), duration of tests, as well as the properties of the polymers (like monomer type, crystallinity index, molecular weight, and chemical additives). This lack of standardization prevented meaningful comparison and integration of results. An additional 5 studies focused exclusively on in vitro and in vivo biodegradation tests, which were not directly relevant to environmental degradation in soil or marine settings, as outlined in the ANIPH DOA. To expand this database, additional experimental data will be required (see Section 2.2.4 below).

2.2.4. Experimental Biodegradation data library of mcl-PHA-based formulations construction

Biodegradation experiments were conducted under controlled laboratory conditions to evaluate the mineralization of PHN material in three different environments: soil, lake water, and compost, under aerobic conditions at 25 °C.

More specifically, each experimental bottle contained approximately 0,40-0,80 g of PHN as the carbon source. The material was placed in 1 L glass incubation bottles together with 160 g of the respective test matrix (for soil and compost) or 400 mL of natural lake water. The water was collected from Lake Mpeletsi, Athens, Greece. The moisture content of the soil was adjusted and maintained at 40 % (w/w) throughout the experiment by periodic rehydration with deionized water as needed. The lake water samples were maintained under continuous magnetic stirring to ensure homogeneous distribution of microorganisms and dissolved oxygen throughout the test period. The bottles were tightly sealed with gas-tight stoppers but were opened every 2-3 days to renew the headspace gas. Between renewals, the bottles remained closed to allow continuous CO₂ accumulation in the trapping system, e.g. an alkaline absorption trap containing 24 mL of 1 N KOH. Each trap was placed inside the incubation bottle in a suspended open container, ensuring no direct contact between the KOH and the test medium. The absorption reaction followed:

During the sampling intervals, the KOH traps were removed, tightly capped, and replaced with fresh solution to maintain continuous CO₂ capture. Moreover, in order to validate biodegradation results, two types of controls were prepared for each environmental condition. A positive control

(cellulose) which was incubated under the same conditions to confirm microbial activity and the responsiveness of the experimental setup and a blank control, containing only the test matrix (no added carbon substrate) to account for background CO₂ evolution from endogenous organic matter and microbial respiration.

The degree of biodegradation was determined as the ratio between the amount of CO₂ generated during the aerobic degradation of the test material and the theoretical CO₂ expected from its complete mineralization. The biodegradation process begins with fragmentation of the polymer by extracellular enzymes secreted by microorganisms, followed by assimilation and mineralization of the resulting fragments into the final products of aerobic metabolism, mainly CO₂, H₂O, inorganic compounds, and a minor fraction of microbial biomass (Briasoulis et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Experimental setup for PHN biodegradation. Images showing the PHN test samples in the lake water system (top row). Laboratory-scale incubation bottles used for the biodegradation experiments in soil, compost, and lake water environments, each equipped with a 1 N KOH CO₂ trap for monitoring mineralization under aerobic conditions at 25 °C (bottom row).

Table 16 below provides a detailed overview of all input (feature) and output (target) variables used to construct the **mcl-PHA's** experimental biodegradation data library. Each presented variable is described in terms of its definition, measurement unit, value range, and type (categorical or numerical). The complete curated raw data library on PHN biodegradation, including all input and output variables, has been uploaded to the [AUA Zenodo repository](#). In Annex (Table A14), an overview of the uploaded data library is presented.

Table 16. Overview of input (feature) and output (target) variables used to construct the mcl-PHA's biodegradation data library.

Variable	Description	Range (Observed)	Type
Instance	Sample instance/reference	1 to 3	Numerical
Sample Name	Name of sample	mPHA-9	Categorical
Monomer	Primary monomer used	PHN	Categorical
mcl_ratio (%)	Monomer composition ratio	100	Numerical
Additive	Presence of additive (Yes/No)	No	Categorical
Degree_of_Biodegradation (%)	Measured degree of biodegradation	0,0 to 10,990 (soil); 0,0 to 0,636 (lake); 0,0 to 5,997 (compost)	Numerical
Time_Points (Days)	Time points used in days	0 to 30	Numerical
Degradation_environment	Medium/environment for degradation	soil, lake water, compost	Categorical
T_biodegradation (Celcius)	Temperature during biodegradation	25	Numerical
Biodegradation_condition	Aerobic/anaerobic	aerobic	Categorical
Parameter_evaluated	Experimental parameter evaluated	Measure CO2 evolved	Categorical
Biodegradation_experimental_method	Method used for experimentation	ISO 17556:2019, ISO 14852:2021	Categorical

Appearance	Physical appearance of material	Pale yellow solid	Categorical
Number_average_Molecular_weight (Mn, kDa)	Number-average molecular weight (kDa)	36,504	Numerical
Molecular_Weight (Mw, kDa)	Weight-average molecular weight (kDa)	60,965	Numerical
Polydispersity Index	Polydispersity index	1,670	Numerical
Tm_1 (°C)	First melting temperature (°C)	61,22	Numerical
Tm_2 (°C)	Second melting temperature (°C)	48,405	Numerical
Td_5% (°C)	Temperature at 5% degradation (°C)	224,1	Numerical
Tensile strength, ultimate (MPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	15,0	Numerical
Modulus (MPa)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	50,0	Numerical
Elongation_at_break (%)	Elongation at break (%)	400,0	Numerical
Specific_density (g/mL)	Specific density (g/mL)	1,0	Numerical
Glass_transition_temperature (°C)	Glass transition temperature (°C)	-46,27	Numerical
Shore_D_Hardness	Shore D hardness	32,0	Numerical
Peak_thermal_degradation_temperature (°C)	Peak thermal degradation temperature (°C)	254,05	Numerical
Viscosity_at_100°C, Pa.s	Viscosity at 100°C (Pa·s)	20,0	Numerical

2.3. Case study for PHAs properties and processability data libraries

Understanding the characteristics of PHAs is fundamental for selecting appropriate materials for a wide range of applications. It is well established that structural modifications within polymer chains can significantly influence their physical and chemical properties. Factors such as molecular weight, degree of crystallinity, PDI (polydispersity index), branching and side chain length, degree of polymerization, chemical composition, monomer units, ratios and structure, the use of additives, melting and glass transition temperature play a crucial role in determining the overall behavior and performance of these polymeric materials (Andraju *et al.*, 2022).

The physical, thermal, mechanical and rheological properties of PHA polymers can be regulated by varying their molecular structures and copolymer compositions (Figure 3), (Getino *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 3. General structure of PHAs. R denotes one of the radicals shown in the table, n represents the number of repetitions of the monomer(s) (which can be arranged in tandem or randomly), and x signifies the number of CH₂ groups within the main chain of each monomer. For the classification of PHAs, the total number of carbons present in the monomer is used, calculated as (R + x + 2). These biopolyesters can be classified based on the carbon chain length (R) of their monomers: short-chain PHAs (4–5 carbons), medium-chain PHAs (6–14 carbons), and long-chain PHAs (more than 14 carbons) (Getino *et al.*, 2024).

The physicochemical properties of scl/mcl PHAs are distinct. Scl-PHAs are more crystalline rigid and brittle with higher melting points than mcl PHAs that are more amorphous and flexible (e.g. could act like a plasticizer in a blend with scl PHA), with higher elasticity and lower melting temperature. The incorporation of HA comonomers (e.g HV) or blends with other PHAs can improve the overall properties and processability of the polymeric materials for optimization for specific applications. Also, properties can be tailored by incorporating specific additives.

As mentioned earlier, polymer databases and data libraries play a crucial role in consolidating research data and understanding the properties of different polymers. They also serve as valuable resources for polymer informatics, machine learning-based property prediction and materials design. Polymer informatics has emerged as a rapidly advancing and highly promising field, demonstrating significant progress and growing research interest in recent years. Currently, there are only a few comprehensive databases and ML models specifically dedicated to PHAs. Two known ML models to predict T_g and T_m and only one that predicts more than one property (13 properties) (Pilania et al., 2019; Bejagam et al., 2022; Kuenneth et al., 2022;).

While several polymer-related databases exist, they are often not open access or are limited in scope, focusing on specific properties rather than offering broad, accessible information on PHAs. To address this limitation, we developed a dedicated database focused on scl-PHAs and mcl PHAs (Andraju *et al.*, 2022; Chen et al. 2021Zhao et al., 2023).

2.3.1. Processability and Products properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV) and their blends (scl/mcl-PHAs)

The data search for construction of a database regarding thermal and mechanical properties of the PHB(V) biopolymer was conducted through the Scopus database. Scopus is a leading abstract and citation database that provides access to a vast collection of peer-reviewed research articles, conference proceedings, and patents. It is a valuable tool for scientific literature review and data analysis.

Table 17. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of scl-PHAs materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("PHBV" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "PHB" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate") AND ("mechanical" OR "thermal" OR "rheological") AND ("lignin" OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR "fructose" OR "glucose" OR "sucrose" OR "lactose" OR "maltose" OR "melezitose" OR "dextran" OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "lignins" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR "limonene" OR "thymol" OR "starch-based	289 Documents

fillers" OR "sorbitol" OR "maltodextrin" OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "PHN" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxynonanoate)"))	
---	--

Using targeted keywords and search phrases, the search query (Table 17, above) was developed, resulting in the retrieval of 289 documents from various scientific databases. In order to select relevant studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as showcased in Table 18 below.

After identifying 118 studies that met the search criteria, a detailed examination of each study followed. Specifically, the goal was to select studies that reported the thermal, mechanical, and rheological properties of the PHB/PHBV compounds for a wide range of molecular weights, as well as the percentages of the two monomers that constituted it. Special emphasis was also placed on studies that included the requested additives.

Table 18. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of scl-PHAs materials.

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on physicochemical, thermal and mechanical properties of PHB/PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on physicochemical, thermal and mechanical properties of PHB/PHBV formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

The data from the examined studies were entered into a database that was created in an Excel environment and was composed of 4 worksheets (Table 19). A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations contained in the dataset. Each worksheet represented a different category of data, which were organized as follows in Tables 19 & 20:

Table 19. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV Formulations).

Worksheet	Features
1. Physicochemical Information (included information regarding the physicochemical properties of the biopolymer)	percentage of the monomer, Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), Percentage of the monomer Polyhydroxyvalerate (PHV), weight average molecular weight (M_w), number average molecular weight (M_n), density of the polymer, polydispersity index (PDI), the existence of additive, the additive name, the percentage of the additive used, etc.

2. Thermal properties (included information on the thermal behavior and characteristics of the polymer)	glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss ($T_{d5\%}$), degradation temperature (T_{deg}), heat of melting fusion (ΔH_m), heat of crystallization fusion (ΔH_c), crystallinity (X_c), etc.
3. Mechanical properties (included details on the mechanical behavior of the polymer)	young modulus, tensile strength, stress at break, yield strength, elongation at break, etc.
4. Metadata (contained information about the title and DOI of each study that were studied)	Study_id, Author, Date, Title, Doi

Table 20. Overview of Input (Feature) and Output (Target) Variables Used to Construct the Materials processability and products properties data library of scl-PHAs.

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	categorical
Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	categorical
Monomer A, Monomer B	Primary monomers	None	HB, HV	categorical
3HB_ratio	Initial 3-hydroxybutyrate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HV_ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyvalerate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
HB_ratio_formulation	3-hydroxyvalerate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
HV_ratio_formulation	3-hydroxyvalerate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
Molecular Weight (Mw)	Weight-average molar mass	g/mol	23900-4400000	numerical
Molecular Weight (Mn)	Number-average molar mass	g/mol	35575-2101000	numerical

Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Polydispersity Index	ratio	1,06-7	numerical
Density	Density of the polymer	g/cm ³	1,09-1.25	numerical
Density_units	Units of density	g/cm ³	-	categorical
Additive_1, Additive_2	Existence of Additives	None	Yes/No	categorical
Additive_1 name Additive_2 name	Name of the additive(s)	None	varies	categorical
Additive_1 Percentage, Additive_2 Percentage	Additive_1 content Additive_2 content	%	0-100	numerical
Additive_Type	Type of additive (e.g. filler, plasticizer)	None	varies	categorical
PHB(V)_percentage	PHBV content in final formulation	%	0-100	numerical
Tg1, Tg2	Glass transition temperature	Celsius (°C)	-48 to 43	numerical
Tc1,Tc2, Tmc	Crystallization temperature	Celsius (°C)	15,5-132	numerical
Tm1, Tm2	Melting temperature	Celsius (°C)	52-180	numerical
Td5	Degradation temperature where 5% of the material's mass has decomposed	Celsius (°C)	158-329	numerical
Tdeg	Degradation temperature	Celsius (°C)	240,4-455	numerical
Temperature_units	Units of temperature	Celsius (°C)	-	categorical
DHm1, DHm2	enthalpy change (DH) associated with the melting process	Joule/gram (J/g)	0,5-109.3	numerical

DHc1, DHc2	enthalpy change (DH) associated with the crystallization process	Joule/gram (J/g)	0,013-97,1	numerical
Enthalpy_units	Units of enthalpy	Joule/gram (J/g)	-	categorical
Crystallinity	degree to which a material has a well-ordered, repeating atomic or molecular structure	%	0-100	numerical
ISO/ASTM	Test standard followed	None	varies	categorical
T_mech, T_mech_units	Temperature for mechanical test	Celsius (°C)	20-25	numerical
Spread_speed, Spread_units	Crosshead speed of mechanical test	mm/min	0,1-50	numerical
Morphology	shape of specimen	-	varies	categorical
Size_diameter,length,width,thickness, Size_units	Dimensions of sample	mm	0,05-210	numerical
Young_modulus	Young's modulus (modulus of elasticity)	MPa	5,42 to 4940	numerical
Ultimate_Tensile_strength	maximum amount of tensile (pulling) stress a material can withstand before breaking	MPa	0,8-258,7	numerical
Stress_at_break	tensile stress a material experiences at the point it actually fractures	Mpa	1,47-34,8	numerical
Yield_strength	the stress threshold where materials shift from elastic behaviour	MPa	2-36	numerical

	(reversible deformation) to plastic behaviour (permanent deformation)			
Mechanical_units	units of mechanical properties and moduli	MPa	-	categorical
Elongation_at_break	the strain (or deformation) a material undergoes from its original length until it fractures, expressed as a percentage of the original length.	%	0,4-970	numerical
Metadata				
Feature	Description			
Study_id	Unique identifier assigned to each study entry			
Author	Name(s) of the author(s) of the study			
Date	Publication date			
Title	Title of the publication or study			
Doi	Digital Object Identifier for the referenced study			

Each study was assigned a unique identification number (study ID). Then, the necessary information from each category was entered into a row. If a study included different physicochemical or experimental details, a separate category (instance) was created for each study. Despite representing different conditions, these categories retained the study ID of their respective source studies.

2.3.2. Processability and Products properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs and their blends (mcl/scl-PHAs)

The database for **mcl-PHAs**, was focused on the physicochemical, thermal, and mechanical properties of medium-chain-length PHAs (homopolymers and copolymers) and their blends with scl PHAs (PHB/PHBV), with different additives and building blocks.

The search for data on the physicochemical, thermal, and mechanical properties of mcl-PHAs and their blends with scl-PHAs was carried out using the advanced search function of the Scopus database with two targeted queries (Table 21) resulting in 181 documents. So far, 114 relevant studies were identified based on predefined criteria, as showcased in Table 22 below, and subsequently subjected to a detailed review. Priority was given to studies reporting thermal and mechanical property data for mcl-PHAs and their blends with scl-PHAs, with particular emphasis on those incorporating the specific additives of interest.

Table 21. Literature Search Queries and Results for thermal and mechanical properties of mcl-PHAs materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("thermal" OR "mechanical"OR"Differential scanning calorimetry "OR"DMA"OR"Dynamic mechanical analysis"OR"TGA"OR"Thermogravimetric analysis")	152 Documents
TITLE-ABS-KEY("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("thermal" OR "mechanical") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY("lignin" OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR "fructose" OR "glucose" OR "sucrose" OR "lactose" OR "maltose" OR "melezitose" OR "dextran" OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "lignins" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR "limonene" OR "thymol" OR "starch-based fillers" OR "sorbitol" OR "maltodextrin" OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "PHBV" OR "poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate")	29 Documents

Table 22. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on thermal and mechanical properties of mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with scl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on thermal and mechanical properties of mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with scl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

The data from the examined studies were entered into a database that was created in an Excel environment and included 4 worksheets (Table 23). A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations contained in the dataset. Each worksheet represented a different category of data, which were organized as follows in Tables 23 & 24.

Table 23. Overview of Worksheets and Parameters in the Thermal and Mechanical Properties Data Libraries of mcl-PHAs.

Worksheet	Features
1. Physicochemical Information, which included information regarding the physicochemical properties of the biopolymer	percentage of short chain length PHA monomer (total), percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxybutyrate (3HB)-C4, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxyvalerate (3HV)-C5, percentage of medium-chain-length PHA monomer (total), percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxyhexanoate (3HHx) – C6, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxyheptanoate (3HHp) – C7, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxyoctanoate (3HO) – C8, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxynonanoate (3HN) – C9, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxydecanoate (3HD) – C10, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxyundecanoate (3HUD) – C11, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxydodecanoate (3HDD) – C12, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxytridecanoate (3HTR) – C13, percentage of the monomer 3-Hydroxytetradecanoate (3HTD) – C14, percentage of unsaturated monomers (unsaturated side chain PHAs), weight average molecular weight (Mw), number average molecular weight (Mn), density of the polymer, polydispersity index (PDI), the type of additive (or blend), the existence of additive (or blend), the additive name (or blend), the percentage of the additive (or blend) used, the final PHA percentage.
2. Thermal properties, which included information on the thermal behavior and characteristics of the polymer.	glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss ($T_{d5\%}$), degradation temperature (T_{deg}), heat of melting fusion (ΔH_m), heat of crystallization fusion (ΔH_c), crystallinity (X_c), etc.
3. Mechanical properties, which included details on the mechanical behavior of the polymer	young modulus, tensile strength, stress at break, yield strength, elongation at break, etc.
4. Metadata, which contains information about the title and DOI of each study that was studied	Study_id, Author, Date, Title, Doi

Table 24. Overview of Processability and Product Properties Data Library of mcl-PHAs Formulations.

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Study_id	Unique identifier for study instance	None	varies	categorical
Instance	Experimental run number	None	varies	categorical
scl PHA ratio	Initial short chain length PHA ratio (3-5 atoms of C)	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HB_ratio	Initial 3-hydroxybutyrate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HV_ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyvalerate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
mcl PHA ratio	Initial medium chain length PHA ratio (6-14 atoms of C)	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HHx ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyhexanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HHp ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyheptanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HO ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyoctanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HN ratio	Initial 3-hydroxynonanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxydecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HUD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxyundecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HDD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxydodecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical

3HTriD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxytridecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
3HTTD ratio	Initial 3-hydroxytetradecanoate ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
Unsaturated monomer ratio	Initial unsaturated monomer ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
Unknown monomer ratio	Initial unknown PHA ratio	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_scl PHA ratio	short chain length PHA ratio (3-5 atoms of C) in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HB ratio	3-hydroxybutyrate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HV ratio	3-hydroxyvalerate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_mcl PHA ratio	medium chain length PHA ratio in formulation(6-14 atoms of C)	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HHx ratio	3-hydroxyhexanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HHp ratio	3-hydroxyheptanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HO ratio	3-hydroxyoctanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HN ratio	3-hydroxynonanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HD ratio	3-hydroxydecanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HUD ratio	3-hydroxyundecanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HDD ratio	3-hydroxydodecanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical

formulation_3HTriD ratio	3-hydroxytridecanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_3HTTD ratio	3-hydroxytetradecanoate ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_Unsaturated monomer ratio	unsaturated monomer ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
formulation_Uknown monomer ratio	unknown PHA ratio in formulation	mol%	0-100	numerical
Molecular Weight (Mw)	Weight-average molar mass	g/mol	23900-4400000	numerical
Molecular Weight (Mn)	Number-average molar mass	g/mol	35575-2101000	numerical
Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Polydispersity Index	ratio	1,06-7	numerical
Density	Density of the polymer	g/cm ³	1,2-1,25	numerical
Density_units	Units of density	g/cm ³	-	categorical
Additive_1,Additive_2	Existence of Additives	None	Yes/No	categorical
Additive_1 name Additive_2 name	Name of the additive(s)	None	varies	categorical
Additive_1 Percentage Additive_2 Percentage	Additive_1 content Additive_2 content	%	0-100	numerical
Additive_Type	Type of additive (e.g. filler, plasticizer)	None	varies	categorical
PHA_percentage	PHA content in final formulation	%	0-100	numerical

In cases of blends of mcl-PHAs with scl-PHAs, the indication of blend occurrence or not, the specific components involved, and their respective ratios were stated under “Additive existence”, “Additive type”, “Additive name”, “Additive percentage” and “final PHA percentage” columns within the “Physicochemical information worksheet”. At instances where such blends include an additive, three additional columns were presented to display the relevant additive-related data. For thermal properties, mechanical properties and metadata worksheets the same organizational framework as the database previously developed for scl-PHAs was applied (e.g. Section 2.3.1).

Each study was given a unique identification number (study ID). The title, author, date, study ID, and DOI number were recorded in a row. If a study involved varying physicochemical or experimental conditions, a new category (instance) was created for each variation. Despite representing different conditions, these categories retained the study ID of their respective source studies.

2.3.3. Rheological Properties Data Libraries of scl-PHAs (PHB/PHBV), mcl-PHAs and their blends (scl/mcl-PHAs)

The growing interest in biodegradable polymers, particularly PHAs, has driven significant research into their material properties and processing behavior. Among these, rheological properties are critical for understanding and optimizing manufacturing techniques such as extrusion, injection molding, and film formation. However, existing data on PHA rheology is often scattered, inconsistent and limited, making it difficult to compare materials or predict processing outcomes. The construction of a comprehensive, standardized dataset for the rheological properties of PHAs is therefore essential. Such a resource would facilitate material selection, process modeling, and the development of new PHA-based products, while also supporting broader efforts to replace conventional plastics with sustainable alternatives. Also, the database for rheological properties of PHAs will be used as a tool for ANIPH AI predictive systems.

2.3.3.1 scl-PHAs formulations’ rheological database construction

Data collection from Scopus

The database for rheological properties of scl-PHAs, was focused on the rheological and viscoelastic properties, describing flow and deformation behavior of short-chain-length PHAs (PHB/PHBV) (homopolymers and copolymers) and their blends with medium-chain-length PHAs, with different additives and building blocks.

The data search for the construction of the database of rheological properties of scl-PHAs was conducted through Scopus, with two targeted queries (Table 25), resulting in 347 documents.

Table 25. Literature Search Queries and Results for rheological properties of scl-PHAs materials

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("PHBV" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA" OR "PHB" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate") AND (rheolog* OR viscosity OR "loss modulus" OR "storage modulus" OR viscoelastic* OR shear*) AND ("lignin" OR "ascorbic acid" OR "orotic acid" OR "theobromine" OR "fructose" OR "glucose" OR "sucrose" OR "lactose" OR "maltose" OR "melezitose" OR "dextran" OR "ascorbyl palmitate" OR "lignins" OR "ammonium quaternary salts" OR "calcium carbonate" OR "acetyl tributyl citrate" OR "epoxidized soybean oil" OR "castor oil" OR "limonene" OR "thymol" OR "starch-based fillers" OR "sorbitol" OR "maltodextrin" OR "hexadecyl 3,5-bis-tert-butyl-4-hydroxybenzoate" OR "PHN" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxynonanoate)"))	56 Documents
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("PHBV" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate" OR "Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)" OR "polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA" OR "PHB" OR "polyhydroxybutyrate") AND (rheolog* OR viscosity OR "loss modulus" OR "storage modulus" OR viscoelastic* OR shear* OR "dynamic frequency sweep" OR "DMA" OR "dynamic mechanical analysis" OR "rheological properties" OR "rotational" OR "viscous" OR "steady shear" OR "complex viscosity" OR "Melt Flow Index" OR "Capillary rheometry" OR "creep test" OR "relaxation test" OR "phase shift" OR "rheology"))	291 Documents

After data curation, 61 research papers were finally selected based on predefined criteria, as showcased in Table 26 below, and subsequently subjected to a detailed review and included into the database that was created in an Excel environment and included 10 worksheets (Tables 27 & 28, below). A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations contained in the database and three extra tabs were created to ensure uniformity of units for storage modulus, loss modulus and angular frequency

Table 26. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Rheological Data Libraries of scl-PHAs

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on rheological and viscoelastic properties of scl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on rheological and viscoelastic properties of scl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with mcl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

For the first two worksheets (e.g. Physicochemical Information and Thermal Properties) and the metadata worksheet of Table 27, the same organizational framework was followed as for the database developed in Section 2.3.1, which was previously developed for scl-PHAs.

Regarding the rheological experimental details, which included information about the type of the test and the experimental conditions, a new worksheet was employed as shown in Tables 27 & 28. More specifically, the 'Test Type' column describes whether a dynamic frequency sweep test (DFS) or a dynamic temperature sweep test (DTS) was used. During DFS, a frequency sweep occurs (with constant temperature and strain or stress), whilst in DTS frequency and strain or stress remain constant and a temperature sweep occurs. These were the two different rheological tests that have been included so far and all the information that each paper stated about the test has been included in the same tab. In both cases, the corresponding diagram of the test shows:

- On the x-axis: either temperature or angular frequency.
- On the y-axis: one or more of the following properties: complex viscosity, storage modulus, loss modulus, or tandelta.

The numerical values were stored in different sheets (Table 27), depending on each specific diagram/test. In each cell/row where at least one of the above properties (complex viscosity, storage modulus, loss modulus, tandelta) was present, there was a corresponding angular frequency or temperature value (depending on whether the test type is DFS or DTS) in the corresponding sheet, referring to the same data instance. In cases where more than one viscoelastic property was available, the data points were selected so that they shared the same x-value (temperature or angular frequency). Therefore, a single x-value may correspond to more than one property.

Table 27. Overview of Rheological Parameters and Datasets for scl-PHAs.

Worksheet	Features
1. Physicochemical Information, which included information regarding the physicochemical properties of the biopolymer	percentage of the monomer Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), percentage of the monomer Polyhydroxyvalerate (PHV), weight average molecular weight (M_w), number average molecular weight (M_n), density of the copolymer, polydispersity index (PDI), the existence of additives, the additive name, the percentage of the additive used, etc.
2. Thermal properties, which included information on the thermal behavior and characteristics of the polymer	glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss ($T_{d5\%}$), degradation temperature (T_{deg}), heat of melting fusion (ΔH_m), heat of crystallization fusion (ΔH_c), crystallinity (X_c), etc.
3. Rheological_experimental_details	Test type constant parameters morphology, etc.
4. storage modulus (G')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
4a. converted (Mpa) storage modulus (G')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
5. loss modulus (G'')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
5a. converted (Mpa) loss modulus (G'')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
6. angular frequency (ω)	angular frequency (ω) at each measurement point during frequency sweep
6a. converted (rad/s) angular frequency (ω)	angular frequency (ω) at each measurement point during frequency sweep

7. Temperature	The temperature at each measurement point during temperature sweep
8. complex viscosity (η^*)	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
9. Tandelata, dumping factor of the sample	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
10. Metadata, which contains information about the title and DOI of each study that was studied	Study_id Author Date Title Doi

Table 28. Summary of Rheological and Mechanical Parameters for scl- and mcl-PHAs.

WorkSheet 3: Rheological_experimental_details				
Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
Test type	information about test types that were recorded (dynamic frequency sweep, dynamic temperature sweep)	None	DFS, DTS	categorical
constant parameters	parameters that stayed constant during the test	None	temperature, angular frequency, stress, strain	categorical
geometry	geometry of the instrument used	None	parallel plate, cone-plate	categorical
plate diameter	diameter of the plate used	mm	20-50	numerical
gap size	gap size used at the test	mm	0,5-2	numerical
morphology	shape of specimen	None	disc, rectangular bars	categorical
diameter	Diameter of sample	mm	5-25	numerical

thickness	thickness of sample	mm	0,5-2	numerical
Angular_frequency_units	units of angular frequency that was used	Hz, rad/s	-	categorical
Texp, Texp_units	Temperature of the experiment (DFS)	Celsius (°C)	145-200	numerical
Viscosity_units	units of complex viscosity	Pa·s	-	categorical
Modulus_units	units of modulus recorded	Pa, Mpa, Gpa, dyne/cm ²	-	categorical
Strain_fixed(%)	constant strain of the test	%	0,02-15	numerical
Frequency_experimental_fixed (Hz)	constant angular frequency of the test (DTS)	Hz	1	numerical

WorkSheet 4 storage modulus (G')

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
storage modulus (G')	a measure of the stored energy in a material during deformation, reflecting its elastic or 'solid-like' behavior. (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)	Pa, Mpa, Gpa, dyne/cm ²	0,09 to 20090928126087400	numerical

WorkSheet 5 loss modulus (G'')				
Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
loss modulus (G'')	a measure of the energy dissipated as heat during deformation, reflecting the material's viscous or 'liquid-like' behavior. (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)	Pa, Mpa, Gpa, dyne/cm ²	0,09to 736207097 494742	numerical

WorkSheet 6 angular frequency (ω)				
Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
angular frequency (ω)	angular frequency (ω) at each measurement point during frequency sweep	rad/s, Hz	0,01- 632,164	numerical

WorkSheet 7 Temperature				
Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
temperature (Texp)	The temperature at each measurement point during temperature sweep	Celsius (°C)	-98 to 200	numerical

WorkSheet 8 complex viscosity (η^*)				
Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
complex viscosity (η^*)	describes the overall resistance of a viscoelastic material	Pa·s	0,03- 83614152, 61	numerical

	to deformation under oscillatory flow.			
	a measure of a fluid's total resistance to flow under an oscillatory or sinusoidal stress			

WorkSheet 9 Tandelata, dumping factor of the sample

Feature	Description	Units	Range	Type
tan delta	ratio of the loss modulus to the storage modulus, damping factor (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)	-	0,04-7,43	numerical

2.3.3.2 mcl-PHAs formulations' rheological database construction

The database for rheological properties of mcl-PHAs, was focused on the rheological and viscoelastic properties of medium-chain-length PHAs (homopolymers and copolymers) and their blends with short-chain-length PHAs (PHB/PHBV), with different additives and building blocks.

The data search for the construction of the database of rheological properties of mcl-PHAs was conducted through Scopus, with a targeted query. Using targeted keywords and phrases, the search query (Table 29) was developed, resulting in the retrieval of 101 documents from various scientific databases. In order to select relevant studies, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as showcased in Table 30 below. After identifying the studies that met the search criteria, a detailed examination of each study followed.

Table 29. Literature Search Queries and Results for rheological properties of mcl-PHAs materials.

Search Query	Results
TITLE-ABS-KEY (("polyhydroxyhexanoate" OR "polyhydroxyheptanoate" OR "polyhydroxyoctanoate" OR "polyhydroxynonanoate" OR "polyhydroxydecanoate" OR "medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate" OR "mcl-PHA"OR"PHBV blend"OR"PHA blend"OR"PHN") AND (101 Documents

"rheological" OR "viscosity" OR "loss modulus" OR "storage modulus" OR "viscoelastic" OR "shear"OR"dynamic frequency sweep"OR"DMA"OR"dynamic mechanical analysis" OR"rheological properties"OR"rotational"OR"viscous"OR"steady shear"OR"complex viscosity"OR"Melt Flow Index"OR"Capillary rheometry"OR"creep test"OR"relaxation test"OR"phase shift"OR"rheology")	
---	--

Table 30. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Rheological Data Libraries on mcl-PHAs

Focus	Inclusion	Exclusion
Scope	The creation of the data libraries focused on rheological and viscoelastic properties of mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with scl-PHAs.	Studies not focused on rheological and viscoelastic properties of mcl-PHAs formulations, with or without additives, and their blends with scl-PHAs.
Publication Language	English	Non-English languages such as French, Chinese, Spanish
Research Design	Primary Studies	Review Articles

After data curation, **11** research papers were selected and included to the database that was created in an Excel environment and included 10 worksheets. A separate tab was included to provide the list of abbreviations contained in the database. Each of the 10 worksheets represented a different category of data and was organized as shown in overview of Table 28 and below in Table 31.

For the first two worksheets (e.g. Physicochemical Information and Thermal Properties) and the metadata worksheet, the same organizational framework was followed as for the database in Section 2.3.2, which was previously developed for mcl-PHAs. For all the rest worksheets (storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G''), angular frequency (ω), temperature (T_{exp}), complex viscosity (η^*) and Tan delta the same organizational framework as the database previously developed for rheological properties of scl-PHAs was applied. (e.g. Section 2.3.3.1). A time worksheet was created to record time-sweep measurements. However, only one of the reviewed papers included this information, so this worksheet will likely be omitted, although it has not been deleted.

Table 31. Overview of Rheological Parameters and Datasets for mcl-PHAs.

Worksheet	Features
1. Physicochemical Information, which included information regarding the physicochemical properties of the biopolymer	percentage of short chain length PHA monomers percentage of medium-chain-length PHA monomers weight average molecular weight (M_w),

	number average molecular weight (M_n), density of the polymer, polydispersity index (PDI), the type of additive (or blend), the existence of additive (or blend), the additive name (or blend), the percentage of the additive (or blend) used, the final PHA percentage.
2. Thermal properties, which included information on the thermal behavior and characteristics of the polymer	glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss ($T_{d5\%}$), degradation temperature (T_{deg}), heat of melting fusion (ΔH_m), heat of crystallization fusion (ΔH_c), crystallinity (X_c), etc.
3. Rheological_experimental_detail	Test type constant parameters morphology, etc.
4. storage modulus (G')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
4a. converted storage modulus (G')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
5. loss modulus (G'')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
5a. converted loss modulus (G'')	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
6. angular frequency (ω)	angular frequency (ω) at each measurement point during frequency sweep
6a. converted angular frequency (ω)	angular frequency (ω) at each measurement point during frequency sweep
7. Temperature	The temperature at each measurement point during temperature sweep
8. complex viscosity (η^*)	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
9. Tandelta, dumping factor of the sample	Data points (at specific angular frequency or at specific temperature)
10. Metadata, which contains information about the title and DOI of each study that was studied	Study_id, Author, Date, Title, Doi

The complete curated raw data libraries on scl- and mcl-PHAs' properties and processability, including all input and output variables, have been uploaded to the [AUA Zenodo repository](#).

3. Conclusions

Deliverable **D2.8** successfully provides the foundational ANIPH Data Libraries, a set of structured, high-quality datasets that feed into the project's AI-driven predictive and traceability systems. These curated datasets ensure full alignment with the FAIR principles and the SSbD methodology. They directly support the implementation of Deliverables D2.5, D2.6, and D2.7, enhancing the reproducibility, transparency, and predictive capacity of biodegradation, processability, and (eco)toxicity assessments across subsequent work packages (WP3, WP4, WP5, WP8, WP9, and WP10). Consequently, **D2.8** establishes a key reference point for developing AI models, supporting end-of-life validation, and advancing sustainable biopolymer development under realistic environmental conditions, while also contributing to the achievement of Milestone 3 (*'ANIPH AI Predictive System and IT platform/tools ready'*).

The creation of comprehensive and standardized data libraries for PHAs represents a major milestone toward data-driven design, evaluation, and optimization of sustainable biopolymers within the ANIPH framework. Through systematic literature review and data integration, a series of curated databases have been established covering cytotoxicity, ecotoxicity, biodegradation, and material properties of both **scl-PHAs** and **mcl-PHAs**, as well as their blends.

The toxicity and ecotoxicity databases provide a structured overview of PHA interactions with biological systems, enabling preliminary risk assessments and supporting regulatory compliance with REACH and OECD standards. The biodegradation datasets, combining literature and experimental data, describe the environmental fate of PHAs in soil, compost, and aquatic systems. AUA developed high-quality datasets for mcl-based PHAs, mainly PHN, and scl-based PHAs (PHBV formulations), incorporating proposed additives for use in Deliverable D2.5. These datasets enabled the development of ML models to predict degradation percentages based on structural and environmental parameters, alongside experimental validation of model outputs.

Deliverable **D2.8** also emphasizes the manual curation of an extensive open-access dataset aimed at elucidating the influence of chemical structure and environmental conditions on PHA degradation. This data-centric approach advances understanding of the complex relationships between polymer composition and degradation behavior, moving beyond traditional trial-and-error experimentation. Furthermore, the mechanical and rheological property datasets provided essential information for material design, supporting the prediction of polymer behavior during industrial processing.

Thus, the results of **D2.8** establish the fundamental knowledge base for the next phases of the ANIPH project, where ML and (Q)SAR models will be developed to predict PHA properties, performance, and safety. These integrated resources will accelerate innovation in biopolymer development, fostering the transition from fossil-based plastics toward sustainable, safe, and high-performance alternatives suitable for humanitarian applications and broader industrial deployment.

4. References

Abbate, E., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Bracalente, G., Mancini, L., Tosches, D., Rasmussen, K., Bennett, M. J., Rauscher, H., & Sala, S. (2024). *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: Methodological guidance* (JRC138035). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/28450>.

Adeleye, A.T., et al., 2020. Sustainable synthesis and applications of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) from biomass. *Process Biochemistry*, 96, pp.–. doi:10.1016/j.procbio.2020.05.032.

Andraju, N., Curtzwiler, G.W., Yun, J., Kozliak, E. & Ranganathan, P., 2022. Machine-learning-based predictions of polymer and postconsumer recycled polymer properties: A comprehensive review. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 14(38), pp.42771–42790. doi:10.1021/acsami.2c08301.

Anjum, A., Zuber, M., Zia, K.M., Noreen, A., Anjum, M.N. & Tabasum, S., 2016. Microbial production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and its copolymers: A review of recent advancements. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 89, pp.–. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.04.069.

Arcos-Hernández, M.V., Laycock, B., Pratt, S., Donose, B.C., Nikolić, M.A.L., Luckman, P., Werker, A. & Lant, P.A., 2012. Biodegradation in a soil environment of activated sludge-derived polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHBV). *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 97(11), pp.2301–2312. doi:10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2012.07.035.

ASTM International, 2017. ASTM D6691-17: Standard test method for determining aerobic biodegradation of plastic materials in the marine environment by a defined microbial consortium or natural sea water inoculum. Available at: <https://store.astm.org/d6691-17.html> [Accessed day month year].

Badia, J.D., Kittikorn, T., Strömberg, E., Santonja-Blasco, L., Martínez-Felipe, A., Ribes-Greus, A., Ek, M. & Karlsson, S., 2014. Water absorption and hydrothermal performance of PHBV/sisal biocomposites. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 108, pp.166–174. doi:10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2014.04.012.

Bejagam, K.K., Lalonde, J., Iverson, C.N., Marrone, B.L. & Pilania, G., 2022. Machine learning for melting temperature predictions and design in polyhydroxyalkanoate-based biopolymers. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 126(4), pp.934–945. doi:10.1021/acs.jpccb.1c08354.

Bolla, M., Pettinato, M., Perego, P., Ferrari, P.F. & Fabiano, B., 2025. Polyhydroxyalkanoates production from laboratory to industrial scale: A review. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 310(Pt 3), p.143255. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.143255.

Boopathy, R., 2000. Factors limiting bioremediation technologies. *Bioresource Technology*, 74(1), pp.63–67. doi:10.1016/S0960-8524(99)00144-3.

Briassoulis, D., Pikasi, A., Papardaki, N.G. & Mistriotis, A., 2023. Biodegradation of plastics in the pelagic environment of the coastal zone – Proposed test method under controlled laboratory conditions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 907, 168889. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168889.

Chen, L., Pilania, G., Batra, R., Huan, T.D., Kim, C., Kuenneth, C. & Ramprasad, R., 2021. Polymer informatics: Current status and critical next steps. *Materials Science and Engineering: R Reports*, 144, 100595. doi:10.1016/j.mser.2020.100595.

Doi, Y. & Kanesawa, Y., 1992. Biodegradation of microbial polyesters in the marine environment. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 36(2), pp.173–177. doi:10.1016/0141-3910(92)90154-W.

European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), 2017. Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment — Chapter R.6: QSARs and grouping of chemicals (Version 3.0). European Union. doi:10.2823/884050.

European Parliament and Council, 2006. Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing certain previous legislative acts (OJ L 396, 30.12.2006, pp.1–849). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2006/1907/oj> [Accessed day month year].

Federle, T.W., Barlaz, M.A., Pettigrew, C.A., Kerr, K.M., Kemper, J.J., Nuck, B.A. & Schechtman, L.A., 2002. Anaerobic biodegradation of aliphatic polyesters: poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyoctanoate) and poly(epsilon-caprolactone). *Biomacromolecules*, 3(4), pp.813–822. doi:10.1021/bm025520w.

Getino, M., Martín, M. & Chamizo-Ampudia, A., 2024. Insights into the microbial degradation of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs): Advances and prospects. *Microorganisms*, 12(10), 2028. doi:10.3390/microorganisms12102028.

International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2013. *Plastics — Vocabulary (ISO 472:2013)*. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/standard/44102.html> [Accessed day month year].

Ishii, M., Ito, T., Sado, H. & Kuwajima, I., 2024. NIMS polymer database PoLyInfo (I): an overarching view of half a million data points. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials: Methods*, 4(1), 2354649. doi:10.1080/27660400.2024.2354649.

Jayasekara, R., Harding, I., Bowater, I. & Lonergan, G., 2005. Biodegradability of a selected range of polymers and polymer blends and standard methods for assessment of biodegradation. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 13(3), pp.231–251. doi:10.1007/s10924-005-4758-2.

Kim, C., Chandrasekaran, A., Huan, T.D., Das, D. & Ramprasad, R., 2018. Polymer Genome: A data-powered polymer informatics platform for property predictions. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 122(31), pp.17575–17585. doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b02913.

Kuenneth, C., Lalonde, J., Marrone, B.L., Iverson, C.N., Ramprasad, R. & Pilania, G., 2022. Bioplastic design using multitask deep neural networks. *Communications Materials*, 3(1), 96. doi:10.1038/s43246-022-00319-2.

Lee, Y.J., Chen, L., Nistane, J., et al., 2023. Data-driven predictions of complex organic mixture permeation in polymer membranes. *Nature Communications*, 14, 4931. doi:10.1038/s41467-023-40257-2.

Li, Z., Yang, J. & Loh, X.J., 2016. Polyhydroxyalkanoates: Opening doors for a sustainable future. *NPG Asia Materials*, 8, e265. doi:10.1038/am.2016.48.

Ma, R. & Luo, T., 2020. PI1M: A benchmark database for polymer informatics. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 60(10), pp.4684–4690. doi:10.1021/acs.jcim.0c00726.

Meereboer, K.W., Misra, M. & Mohanty, A.K., 2020. Review of recent advances in the biodegradability of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) bioplastics and their composites. *Green Chemistry*, 22, pp.5519–5558. doi:10.1039/D0GC01647K.

Mergaert, J., Anderson, C., Wouters, A., Swings, J. & Kersters, K., 1992. Biodegradation of polyhydroxyalkanoates. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, 9(2–4), pp.317–321. doi:10.1111/j.1574-6968.1992.tb05853.x.

Pilania, G., Iverson, C.N., Lookman, T. & Marrone, B.L., 2019. Machine-learning-based predictive modeling of glass transition temperatures: A case of polyhydroxyalkanoate homopolymers and copolymers. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 59(12), pp.5013–5025. doi:10.1021/acs.jcim.9b00807.

PlotDigitizer, n.d. PlotDigitizer [software]. Available at: <https://plotdigitizer.com/>

Puzyn, T., Jeliaskova, N., Sarimveis, H., Marchese Robinson, R., Lobaskin, V., Rallo, R., Richarz, A.N., Gajewicz, A., Papadopoulos, M.G., Hastings, J., Cronin, T.D.M., Benfenati, E. & Fernández, A., 2018. Perspectives from the NanoSafety Modelling Cluster on the validation criteria for (Q)SAR models used in nanotechnology. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 112, pp.478–494. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2017.09.037.

Sharma, V., Sehgal, R. & Gupta, R., 2021. Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA): Properties and modifications. *Polymer (Guildford)*, 212, 123161. doi:10.1016/j.polymer.2020.123161.

Vinçotte, 2012. OK biodegradable SOIL: Initial acceptance tests (Doc Ref: OK10-e, Edition C). Available at: https://be.tuvaustria.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/73/2024/03/CS-OK10-EN_OK_biodegradable_SOIL.pdf

Vinçotte, 2019. OK biodegradable MARINE: Initial acceptance tests. Available at: <http://www.tuv-at.be/green-marks/doc-center/>

Weng, Y.-X., Wang, X.-L. & Wang, Y.-Z., 2011. Biodegradation behavior of PHAs with different chemical structures under controlled composting conditions. *Polymer Testing*, 30(4), pp.372–380. doi:10.1016/j.polymertesting.2011.02.001.

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., et al., 2016. The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. doi:10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

Zhao, Y., Mulder, R.J., Houshyar, S. & Le, T.C., 2023. A review on the application of molecular descriptors and machine learning in polymer design. *Polymer Chemistry*, 14(29), pp.3325–3346. doi:10.1039/D3PY00395G.

5. Annex

Overview of the Toxicity Data Libraries of scl- and mcl-based formulations.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table A1. Physicochemical Properties in the Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_ id	Instance	Monomer_ A	Monomer_ B	HB_ ratio	HV_ ratio	Mw	Mw_ Units	PDI	Shape
4	1	3HB	3HV	90,2	9,8	92000	g/mol	N/A	Microparticles
4	2	3HB	3HV	90,2	9,8	92000	g/mol	N/A	Microparticles
4	3	3HB	3HV	90,2	9,8	92000	g/mol	N/A	Microparticles
5	1	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	2	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	3	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	4	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	5	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	6	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	7	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	8	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
5	9	3HB	3HV	88	12	609530	g/mol	0,52	Nanoparticle
11	1	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
11	2	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
11	3	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
11	4	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
11	5	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
11	6	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	230000	g/mol	2,3	Fiber
18	1	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	7300	g/mol	N/A	Nanoparticle
18	2	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	7300	g/mol	N/A	Nanoparticle
18	3	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	7300	g/mol	N/A	Nanoparticle
18	4	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	7300	g/mol	N/A	Nanoparticle
18	5	3HB	N/A	100	N/A	7300	g/mol	N/A	Nanoparticle

Diameter	Diameter_Units	Additive	Additive1_Name	Additive1_Percentage	Additive1_Use	Polymers_Percentage
43,21	µm	Yes	RIF	16,67	Antibiotic	66,67
43,21	µm	Yes	RIF	16,67	Antibiotic	66,67
43,21	µm	Yes	RIF	16,67	Antibiotic	66,67
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
208,51	nm	Yes	EPT	42,13	Anticancer	57,87
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	90	Carrier	10
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	81	Carrier	9
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	90	Carrier	10
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	81	Carrier	9
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	90	Carrier	10
2	µm	Yes	PLGA	81	Carrier	9
140	nm	Yes	PMLA	52	Carrier	48
140	nm	Yes	PMLA	52	Carrier	48
140	nm	Yes	PMLA	52	Carrier	48
140	nm	Yes	PMLA	52	Carrier	48
140	nm	Yes	PMLA	52	Carrier	48

Table A2. Experimental Inputs in the Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	ISO	Assay	Cell_Line	Cell_Line_Type	Exposure_type	No_Cells_per_well	Inoculum_concentration_units	Culture_Medium	Dilution_Medium
1	1	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	2	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	3	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	4	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	5	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	6	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	7	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM
1	8	10993-5	LDH	Saos-2	Human	Indirect_contact	10000	cells/well	McCOY_5A_10FBS_PS_Glu_Pyr_HEPES	DMEM

Concentration	Concentration_Units	Incubation_Temperature	Incubation_Temperature_Units	CO ₂ _percentage	Air	Extraction_Time
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	5	Humidified	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	5	Humidified	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	5	Humidified	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	5	Humidified	N/A
N/A	N/A	37	Celsius	5	Humidified	N/A

Units_Extraction_ Time	Extraction_ Temperature	Units_Extraction_ Temperature	Extraction_Medium	Extraction_Surface_Area_Ratio	Extraction_Surface_Area_ Ratio_Units
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,50	(cm ²)/mL
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table A3. Experimental Outputs in the Cytotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations

Study_id	Instance	Number_of_cells_well	Cell_viability_Percentage	Toxicity	Growth_constant_μ	Growth_constant_μ_units	RGR	Toxicity_Grade	Growth_inhibition_percentage
7	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
7	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
7	3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,98	1,00	N/A
7	4	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1,00	0,00	N/A
7	5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
7	6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
7	7	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1,00	0,00	N/A
7	8	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
7	9	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,99	0,00	N/A
11	1	N/A	100,00	Non-toxic	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,00	N/A
11	2	N/A	100,00	Non-toxic	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,00	N/A
11	3	N/A	100,00	Non-toxic	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,00	N/A
11	4	N/A	99,00	Non-toxic	N/A	N/A	N/A	0,00	N/A

Table A4. Physicochemical Properties in the Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Monomer_A	Monomer_B	Monomer_C	3HB_ratio	3HV_ratio	4HV_ratio	Mw	Units_Mw	Mn
4	1	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	2	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	3	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	4	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	5	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	6	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	7	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	8	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	9	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
4	10	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	350200	g/mol	299316
6	1	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	2	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	3	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	4	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	5	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	6	3HB	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Units_Mn	PDI	Shape	Diameter	Diameter_Units	Thickness	Units_Thickness	Additive1	Additive1_Name	Additive1_Percentage	Additive1_Use	Polymer_Percentage
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	50	Plasticizer	50
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	48,5	Plasticizer	48,5
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	46,5	Plasticizer	46,5
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	44	Plasticizer	44
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	50	Plasticizer	50
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	48,5	Plasticizer	48,5
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	46,5	Plasticizer	46,5
N/A	1,17	Film	N/A	N/A	0,15	mm	Yes	PHA	44	Plasticizer	44
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	N/A	Spherical	1,25	µm	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100

Table A5. Experimental Inputs in the Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Species_Name	Species_Group	Initial_Organism_Age	Units_Initial_Organism_Age	Exposure_type	Media_type
1	1	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
1	2	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
1	3	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
1	4	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
1	5	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
1	6	Mouse	Air_Breathing_Animals	N/A	N/A	Orally	N/A
2	1	Hydra_Viridissima	Aquatic_Organisms	2	weeks	Waterborne	Artificial_Freshwater
2	2	Hydra_Viridissima	Aquatic_Organisms	2	weeks	Waterborne	Artificial_Freshwater
2	3	Hydra_Viridissima	Aquatic_Organisms	2	weeks	Waterborne	Artificial_Freshwater
2	4	Hydra_Viridissima	Aquatic_Organisms	2	weeks	Waterborne	Artificial_Freshwater
2	5	Hydra_Viridissima	Aquatic_Organisms	2	weeks	Waterborne	Artificial_Freshwater

Test_location	Tested_Concentration	Units_Testing_Concentration	Observation_Period	Units_Observation_Period	Toxicity
Lab	125	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	250	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	500	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	1000	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	1500	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	2000	mg/kg	24	hours	Acute
Lab	0,001	mg/L	4	days	Acute
Lab	0,01	mg/L	4	days	Acute
Lab	0,1	mg/L	4	days	Acute
Lab	1	mg/L	4	days	Acute
Lab	10	mg/L	4	days	Acute

Table A6. Experimental Outputs in the Ecotoxicity Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	EC_50	EC_50_Units	LD_50	LD_50_Units	Mortality_Percentage	SGI_Percentage	Toxicity_Grade	Toxicity_Classification
1	1	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	0	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
1	2	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	0	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
1	3	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	0	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
1	4	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	25	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
1	5	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	50	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
1	6	N/A	N/A	1500	mg/kg	75	N/A	1	Toxic
2	1	6,3	mg/L	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	Toxic
2	2	6,3	mg/L	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	Toxic
2	3	6,3	mg/L	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	Toxic
2	4	6,3	mg/L	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	Toxic
2	5	6,3	mg/L	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	Toxic
3	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	97	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
3	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
3	3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	97	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
3	4	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100	N/A	2	Moderately_Toxic
4	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,45	0	Non_Toxic
4	3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	98,99	0	Non_Toxic
4	4	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,72	0	Non_Toxic
4	5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,54	0	Non_Toxic
4	6	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,81	0	Non_Toxic
4	7	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,56	0	Non_Toxic
4	8	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,25	0	Non_Toxic
4	9	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	99,85	0	Non_Toxic

Table A7. Physicochemical Properties in the Toxicity Data Library of mcl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	initial_scl PHA ratio	initial_3HB ratio	initial_mcl PHA ratio	3HHx ratio	3HHp ratio	3HO ratio	3HN ratio	3HD ratio	3HUD ratio	3HDD ratio	Mw	Mn
3	1	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	2	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	3	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	4	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	5	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	6	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	7	88	88	12	12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2800
3	15	N/A	N/A	100	1,6	N/A	24,6	N/A	71,2	N/A	2,6	N/A	2300
3	16	N/A	N/A	100	1,6	N/A	24,6	N/A	71,2	N/A	2,6	N/A	2300

PDI	Additive	Additive1_name	Additive1_percentage	Additive2_name	Additive2_percentage	final_PHA_percentage
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
N/A	Yes	PC	70	Cholesterol	28	2
N/A	Yes	PC	70	Cholesterol	28	2

Overview of the Biodegradation Data Libraries of scl- and mcl-based formulations.

Table A8. Overview of the Physicochemical Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-
PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Sample_name	{Sample ratio wt/wt% }	Monomer_A	Monomer_B	Adjusted_HB_ratio_of_formulation (mol%)	Adjusted_HV_ratio_of_formulation (mol%)	Additives	Additive1_name	Additive_type_1
1	1	PHBV (with plasticizer)	90/10	PHB	PHV	79,2	10,8	Yes	Citric Acid	plasticizer
1	2	PLA/PHBV	70/30	PHB	PHV	23,76	3,24	Yes	Citric Acid	plasticizer
1	3	PHBV (with plasticizer)	90/10	PHB	PHV	79,2	10,8	Yes	Citric Acid	plasticizer
1	4	PLA/PHBV	70/30	PHB	PHV	23,76	3,24	Yes	Citric Acid	plasticizer
2	1	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax/alginate acid	68/30/2	PHB	PHV	53,856	7,344	Yes	citric ester	plasticizer
2	2	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax	68/30/2	PHB	PHV	55,44	7,56	Yes	citric ester	plasticizer
2	3	neat PHBV (with plasticizer)	90/10	PHB	PHV	79,2	10,8	Yes	citric ester	plasticizer
3	1	PHBV	100/0	PHB	PHV	98	2	No	N/A	N/A
3	2	PHBV-20Vish-E	80/20	PHB	PHV	78,4	1,6	Yes	Vish-E filler	filler
3	3	PHBV-20Vish-V	80/20	PHB	PHV	78,4	1,6	Yes	Vish-V filler	filler
4	1	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO ₃ /ATBC/PO	66.5/3.5/10/20	PHB	PHV	63,2	3,3	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticizer

4	2	PCA10: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	76/4/10 /10	PHB	PHV	72,2	3,8	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticize r
4	3	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	85.5/4.5 /10	PHB	PHV	81,225	4,275	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticize r
4	4	PCA30: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	57/3/10 /30	PHB	PHV	54,15	2,85	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticize r
4	5	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	66.5/3.5 /10/20	PHB	PHV	63,2	3,3	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticize r
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	85.5/4.5 /10	PHB	PHV	81,225	4,275	Yes	ATBC: acetyl tributyl citrate	plasticize r
5	1	PHBV/SOIL	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A
5	2	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	3	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	4	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	5	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	6	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	7	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	8	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	9	PHBV/SOIL	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A
5	10	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	11	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	12	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	13	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	14	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	15	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	16	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	17	PHBV/SOIL	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A

5	18	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	19	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	20	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	21	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	22	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	23	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	24	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	25	PHBV/LAKE	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A
5	26	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	27	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	28	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	29	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	30	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	31	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	32	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	STARCH	filler
5	33	PHBV/LAKE	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A
5	34	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	35	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	36	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	37	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	38	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	39	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	40	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	CELLULOSE	filler
5	41	PHBV/LAKE	100/0	PHB	PHV	94	6	No	N/A	N/A
5	42	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	90/10	PHB	PHV	84.6	5,4	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	43	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	80/20	PHB	PHV	75.2	4,8	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	44	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	70/30	PHB	PHV	65.8	4,2	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	45	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	60/40	PHB	PHV	56.4	3,6	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	46	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	50/50	PHB	PHV	47.0	3	Yes	ALGINATE	filler

5	47	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	40/60	PHB	PHV	37.6	2,4	Yes	ALGINATE	filler
5	48	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	30/70	PHB	PHV	28.2	1,8	Yes	ALGINATE	filler

Table A9. Overview of the Environmental Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-
PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Sample_name	Parameter_evaluated	Biodegradation_condition	*Degradation_mechanism	T_bio_deg	T_biodeg_units	Degradation_Environment	ASTM/ISO
1	1	PHBV (with plasticizer)	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Hydrolysis-assisted microbial assimilation	58	celsius	industrial compost	ASTM D5338-15
1	2	PLA/PHBV	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Hydrolysis-assisted microbial assimilation	58	celsius	industrial compost	ASTM D5338-15
1	3	PHBV (with plasticizer)	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Hydrolysis-assisted microbial assimilation	24	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
1	4	PLA/PHBV	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Hydrolysis-assisted microbial assimilation	24	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
2	1	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax/alginate	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	58	celsius	compost	ASTM D6400
2	2	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	58	celsius	compost	ASTM D6400

2	3	neat PHBV (with plasticizer)	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	58	celsius	compost	ASTM D6400
3	1	PHBV	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-96
3	2	PHBV-20Vish-E	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-97
3	3	PHBV-20Vish-V	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	28	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-98
4	1	PCA20	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	25	celsius	marine	ASTM D6691
4	2	PCA10	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	25	celsius	marine	ASTM D6691
4	3	PCA	Measure CO2 evolved	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	25	celsius	marine	ASTM D6691
4	4	PCA30	N/A	N/A	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	5	PCA20	changes in the weight	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	N/A	celsius	marine	N/A
4	6	PCA	changes in the weight	aerobic	Enzyme-mediated microbial biodegradation	N/A	celsius	marine	N/A

6	1	PHA20W	oxygen consumption	anaerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	25	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
6	2	PHA20W	oxygen consumption	anaerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	25	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
6	3	PHA50W	oxygen consumption	anaerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	25	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
6	4	PHA20W	oxygen consumption	anaerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	25	celsius	soil	ASTM D5988-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion-driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160-12

6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion– driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	5	PHA0W	weight loss	aerobic	Surface erosion– driven biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12
6	6	PHA20W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160– 12

6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12
6	7	PHA50W	weight loss	aerobic	Crack-enhanced microbial biodegradation	20	celsius	field soil	ASTM G160–12

Table A10. Overview of the Thermal Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Sample_name	Biodegradation_Time_points (days)	Tonset	Tm1	Tm2	Td5	Temperature_units	DHm1	DHc	Enthalpy_units	Crystallinity_index (Xc %), DSC measurements
1	1	PHBV compost	30	240,6	149,4	160,1	240,6	celcius	31,8	45,6	J/g	30
1	1	PHBV compost	200	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1	2	PLA/PHBV compost	30	224,5	N/A	152,1	242,8	celcius	7,8	N/A	J/g	N/A
1	2	PLA/PHBV compost	200	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1	3	PHBV soil	30	224,5	145,4	156,5	N/A	celcius	78,8	43	J/g	74,3
1	3	PHBV soil	200	213,6	146	153,6	N/A	celcius	28,2	59,9	J/g	26,6
1	4	PLA/PHBV soil	30	169,05	142,4	154,3	N/A	celcius	19	4.7	J/g	14,2
1	4	PLA/PHBV soil	200	195,80	N/A	154,1	N/A	celcius	13,6	N/A	J/g	10,2
1	5	PHBV	0	253,7	154,6	162,8	253,7	celcius	77	85,9	J/g	72,6
1	6	PLA/PHBV	0	258,7	143,9	155,6	205,3	celcius	31,8	12,7	J/g	23,8

2	1	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax/alginate	0	180,35	N/A	N/A	180,35	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
2	2	PHBV(with plasticizer)/flax	0	238,09	N/A	N/A	238,09	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
2	3	neat PHBV (with plasticizer)	0	263,09	N/A	N/A	263,09	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
2	4	neat PHBV (with plasticizer)	30	249,69	N/A	N/A	249,69	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	1	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	0	207	N/A	N/A	207	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	2	PCA10: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	0	205	N/A	N/A	205	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	3	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	0	260	N/A	N/A	260	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	4	PCA30: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	0	210	N/A	N/A	210	celcius	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
11	1	PHBV	0	284	155	169	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	46,3
11	2	5P01N	0	285	152	165	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	38,1
11	3	5P03N	0	N/A	154	167	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	36,8
11	4	5P05N	0	N/A	153	165	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	39,3
11	5	7P01N	0	261	150	164	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	44,7

11	6	7P03N	0	N/A	150	164	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	35,8
11	7	7P05N	0	N/A	152	165	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	37,3
11	8	10P01N	0	270	150	163	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	37,1
11	9	10P03N	0	N/A	150	164	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	37,6
11	10	10P05N	0	N/A	151	165	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	36,1
12	1	Pure PHBV	0	261,7 6	171, 19	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	51,5
12	2	PHBV/MAF (10%)	0	273,4 8	172, 94	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	48,35
12	3	PHBV/MAF (20%)	0	272,1 5	172, 8	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	47,14
12	4	PHBV/MAF (30%)	0	268,5 2	172, 5	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	36,12
12	5	PHBV/MAF (40%)	0	266,6 3	172, 23	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	33,5
12	6	PHBV/MAF (50%)	0	262,4 7	172, 09	N/A	N/A	celsius	N/A	N/A	J/g	24,44
16	5	PHBV	0	270,9	169, 6	173 ,3	N/A	celsius	82,2	N/A	J/g	56
16	5a	PHBV	30	260,1	167, 3	171 ,5	N/A	celsius	77,7	N/A	J/g	53
16	5b	PHBV	30	271,8	168, 9	174 ,2	N/A	celsius	83,6	N/A	J/g	57
16	5c	PHBV	30	243,8	167	173 ,1	N/A	celsius	76,2	N/A	J/g	52

16	6	PHBV/ATBC	0	253,2	166,4	170,1	N/A	celsius	80,5	N/A	J/g	61
16	6a	PHBV/ATBC	30	249,8	N/A	169,2	N/A	celsius	79,2	N/A	J/g	60
16	6b	PHBV/ATBC	30	251,4	162,7	169,9	N/A	celsius	72,6	N/A	J/g	55
16	6c	PHBV/ATBC	30	237,2	165,3	170,5	N/A	celsius	73,9	N/A	J/g	56
16	7	PHBV/ATBC/L-CNC	0	254,6	150,8	170,6	N/A	celsius	70,1	N/A	J/g	54
16	7a	PHBV/ATBC/L-CNC	30	251,1	N/A	172,4	N/A	celsius	77	N/A	J/g	59
16	7b	PHBV/ATBC/L-CNC	30	257,7	160,9	171	N/A	celsius	71,2	N/A	J/g	55
16	7c	PHBV/ATBC/L-CNC	30	244,3	161,3	170,2	N/A	celsius	73,1	N/A	J/g	56
16	8	PHBV/ATBC/CaCO ₃	0	237,3	160,6	169,5	N/A	celsius	62,2	N/A	J/g	53
16	8a	PHBV/ATBC/CaCO ₃	30	226,3	N/A	170,8	N/A	celsius	68	N/A	J/g	58
16	8b	PHBV/ATBC/CaCO ₃	30	229,9	161,2	170,3	N/A	celsius	59,8	N/A	J/g	51
16	8c	PHBV/ATBC/CaCO ₃	30	217,3	162,2	169,9	N/A	celsius	63,3	N/A	J/g	54

Table A11. Overview of the Mechanical Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Sample_name	Time_points (days)	Biodegradation_percentage (%)	Morphology	Specimens_shape	ASTM	Young_modulus	Young_modulus_units
3	1	PHBV	0	N/A	matrix	matrix	N/A	2,16	Gpa
3	2	PHBV-20Vish-E	0	N/A	particle	particle	N/A	2,43	Gpa
3	3	PHBV-20Vish-V	0	N/A	particle	particle	N/A	2,5	Gpa
4	1	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	0	N/A	fillament/pellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,72	Gpa
4	2	PCA10: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	0	N/A	fillament/pellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,37	Gpa
4	3	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	0	N/A	fillament/pellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,01	Gpa
<u>4</u>	4	PCA30: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	<u>0</u>	N/A	fillament/pellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	<u>2,38</u>	Gpa
4	1	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	<u>0</u>	N/A	fillament/pellet	Bars	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	2	PCA10: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/PO	<u>0</u>	N/A	fillament/pellet	Bars	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	3	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	<u>0</u>	N/A	fillament/pellet	Bars	N/A	N/A	N/A

<u>4</u>	<u>4</u>	PCA30: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	<u>0</u>	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Bars	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	5	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	30	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,67614	Gpa
4	5	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	90	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	1,98864	Gpa
4	5	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	150	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	1,59091	Gpa
4	5	PCA20: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC/P O	300	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	1,60227	Gpa
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	30	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	1,99432	Gpa
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	90	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,28977	Gpa
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	150	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,29545	Gpa
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	300	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,69886	Gpa
4	6	PCA: PHBV/CaCO3/ATBC	360	N/A	fillament/p ellet	Dog-bone tensile bars	ASTM D 638	2,38068	Gpa
5	1	PHBV/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	181 ± 6,0	Mpa
5	2	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	45 ± 4,3	Mpa

5	3	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	37 ± 4,7	Mpa
5	4	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	28 ± 3,8	Mpa
5	5	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	21 ± 0,9	Mpa
5	6	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	17± 1,5	Mpa
5	7	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	9 +1,7	Mpa
5	8	PHBV/STARCH/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	4±0,7	Mpa
5	9	PHBV/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	181 ± 6,0	Mpa
5	10	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	60 ± 0,7	Mpa
5	11	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	53±3,7	Mpa
5	12	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	30 ± 4,9	Mpa

5	13	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	28±4,9	Mpa
5	14	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	25 ± 3,2	Mpa
5	15	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	18±0,7	Mpa
5	16	PHBV/CELLULOSE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	7± 1,1	Mpa
5	17	PHBV/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	181 ± 6,0	Mpa
5	18	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	34 ± 4,6	Mpa
5	19	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	26 ± 2,4	Mpa
5	20	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	16 ± 0,9	Mpa
5	21	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	14 ± 2,7	Mpa
5	22	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	8 ± 2,0	Mpa

5	23	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$5 \pm 0,6$	Mpa
5	24	PHBV/ALGINATE/SOIL	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$3 \pm 0,0$	Mpa
5	25	PHBV/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$181 \pm 6,0$	Mpa
5	26	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$45 \pm 4,3$	Mpa
5	27	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$37 \pm 4,7$	Mpa
5	28	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$28 \pm 3,8$	Mpa
5	29	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$21 \pm 0,9$	Mpa
5	30	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$17 \pm 1,5$	Mpa
5	31	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$9 \pm 1,7$	Mpa
5	32	PHBV/STARCH/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	$4 \pm 0,7$	Mpa

5	33	PHBV/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	181 ± 6,0	Mpa
5	34	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	60 ± 0,7	Mpa
5	35	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	53±3,7	Mpa
5	36	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	30 ± 4,9	Mpa
5	37	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	28±4,9	Mpa
5	38	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	25 ± 3,2	Mpa
5	39	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	18±0,7	Mpa
5	40	PHBVCELLULOSE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	7± 1,1	Mpa
5	41	PHBV/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	181 ± 6,0	Mpa
5	42	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	34 ± 4,6	Mpa

5	43	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	26 ± 2,4	Mpa
5	44	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	16 ± 0,9	Mpa
5	45	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	14 ± 2,7	Mpa
5	46	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	8 ± 2,0	Mpa
5	47	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	5 ± 0,6	Mpa
5	48	PHBV/ALGINATE/LAKE	0	N/A	circular film	dumbbell shape	steel ASTM regulation punches	3 ± 0,0	Mpa

Table A12. Overview of the Biodegradation Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-
PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Sample_name	Biodegradation_percentage %										
			3,6390099	4,967985197	5,531299561	6,22125376	6,385741384	7,71470553	15,28384178	16,88501504	21,83405968	26,05531344	28,09316123
1	1	PHBV	3,6390099	4,967985197	5,531299561	6,22125376	6,385741384	7,71470553	15,28384178	16,88501504	21,83405968	26,05531344	28,09316123
1	2	PLA/PHBV	5,3857414	6,841345363	8,151391165	11,0625991	14,55603979	17,1761314	19,65065371	24,16303493	28,7796	34,79053	38,09316123
1	3	PHBV	0,9868437	1,096491196	1,315794454	1,4254419	2,192982392	3,07017869	3,837719186	5,701759238	9,758773317	12,93859946	17,32456424
1	4	PLA/PHBV	0,9868437	1,096491196	1,315794454	1,4254419	2,192982392	3,07017869	5,592103426	7,675438372	12,06140316	14,91227859	17,32456424
2	1	alginate treated flax/PHBV	5,9435364	10,99554235	15,75037147	18,7221397	25,70579495	27,6374443	29,12332838	35,21545319	37,74145617	43,53640416	45,46805349
2	2	untreated flax/PHBV	5,794948	7,875185736	10,99554235	11,2927192	13,52154532	15,4531947	19,1679049	22,43684993	27,04309064	30,31203566	34,76968796
2	3	neat PHBV	5,49777	5,05201	5,64636	5,34918	5,34918	4,45765	3,71471	4,90342	6,53789	9,80684	14,56166
3	1	PHBV	4,143650	11,325970	21,546960	34,806630	50,000000	66,022100	84,530390	90,607730	93,370170	96,132600	95,580110
3	2	PHBV-20Vish-E	9,94475	18,78453	25,69061	40,60773	55,24862	73,20442	89,77901	93,09392	95,02762	94,75138	96,13260
3	3	PHBV-20Vish-V	7,18232	15,46961	28,72928	42,54144	55,8011	71,27072	92,54144	96,96133	99,44751	99,72376	99,72376
4	1	PCA20	2,038040	2,717390	2,581520	2,989130	3,260870	3,532610	3,940220	4,211960	4,755430	5,163040	5,570650
4	2	PCA10	1,90217	2,03804	1,63043	1,90217	2,17391	1,90217	1,90217	2,17391	2,58152	3,125	3,125

4	3	PCA	1,4945 7	1,63043	2,03804	2,1739 1	2,44565	2,4456 5	2,58152	3,26087	3,53261	4,07609	4,07609
6	1	PHA20W	1,6816 8	2,64264	3,9039	5,1651 7	5,76577	7,0270 3	6,36637	8,04805	9,18919	10,0900 9	10,9909 9
6	2	PHA20W	1,3213 2	2,28228	3,54354	4,3243 2	5,46547	6,7267 3	8,16817	9,18919	9,84985	10,6906 9	11,5315 3
6	3	PHA50W	0,9009	1,62162	3,24324	3,9639 6	4,8048	5,5255 3	6,36637	7,26727	8,40841	9,36937	10,0900 9
6	4	PHA20W	1,3813 8	2,04204	2,88288	3,7237 2	4,32432	5,2252 3	6,42643	7,14715	8,28829	9,06907	9,78979
7	1	PHBV	12,021 47	12,5939 2	15,1699 5	15,169 95	18,8908 8	24,329 16	26,0465 1	29,7674 4	34,6332 7	42,9338 1	50,0894 5
7	2	PHBV-Q	11,735 24	11,4490 2	11,7352 4	14,597 5	15,4561 7	19,177 1	22,3255 8	24,3291 6	26,3327 4	32,0572 5	39,4991 1
7	3	PHBV-GA	9,1592 1	8,87299	9,73166	9,4454 4	10,3041 1	12,307 69	14,3112 7	15,7424	18,6046 5	22,0393 6	27,7638 6
15	1	PHBV	2,8985 5	12,5	16,4855 1	23,007 25	27,3550 7	33,695 65	38,9492 8	43,1159 4	45,4710 2	47,2826 1	50
15	2	PHBV/TC	7,3839 8	10,6448 2	21,5686 1	24,503 36	27,6011 5	30,046 78	33,3076 1	36,2423 6	37,7097 3	40,1553 6	42,1118 6
15	3	PHBV/WF	4,5289 8	12,8623 2	19,4490 7	22,057 73	25,3185 7	29,891 31	32,4275 4	36,0507 3	40,0362 3	43,2971	45,2096 5
16	1	PHBV	2,5134 8	3,5056	5,3481	8,0409 8	10,8755 9	13,710 21	16,5448 2	19,3794 4	22,2140 5	25,0486 7	27,8832 8
16	2	PHBV/ATBC	3,0804 1	4,49771	6,62367	9,4582 9	12,2929	15,127 52	17,9621 3	20,7967 4	23,6313 6	26,4659 7	32,1352
16	3	PHBV/ATBC/L -CNC	1,6631	2,23002	3,36387	5,0646 4	7,75752	10,592 13	13,4267 5	16,2613 6	19,0959 8	21,9305 9	24,7652
16	4	PHBV/ATBC/C aCO3	3,2221 4	5,77329	8,6079	11,442 52	14,2771 3	17,111 75	19,9463 6	22,7809 7	25,6155 9	28,4502	31,2848 2

20	1	neat PHBV	2,5751	9,01287	12,2317 6	20,171 66	24,0343 3	30,472 1	37,1244 7	42,4892 7	49,3562 2	53,0042 9	57,2961 4
20	2	phbv sep straw/90:10	7,2961 4	11,1588	13,9484 9	16,309	19,0987 1	23,175 97	26,8240 3	33,2618	37,9828 3	44,8497 8	45,9227 5
20	3	phbv sep straw/80:20	5,7939 9	7,51072	14,3776 7	20,171 66	24,6781 1	28,969 96	34,3347 6	40,3433 4	44,4206	48,7124 4	51,9313 3
20	4	phbv sep straw/70:30	5,3648 1	7,72532	13,0901 3	18,240 33	22,7467 8	28,326 17	32,4034 3	36,9098 7	42,0600 9	46,3519 3	51,0729 6
22	1	PHBV	33,328 23	37,3194 9	40,6064 1	43,188 99	45,3020 1	47,884 59	49,7628 3	52,1106 3	54,9279 9	55,8671 1	59,1540 3
22	2	PHBV/Misc 85/15	9,3806 7	14,7806 1	21,3544 5	26,050 05	30,0413 1	35,910 81	38,4933 9	41,3107 5	46,6956 5	52,5801 9	54,2608 7
22	3	PHBV/Misc 75/25	21,130 43	26,9891 7	30,9804 3	35,206 47	38,2586 1	41,310 75	45,5367 9	50,3478 2	58,4347 8	60,0000 1	63,3800 7
22	4	PHBV/ DDGS 85/15	8,6763 3	15,2501 7	21,8240 1	26,608 7	30,5217 5	40,136 85	45,0672 3	49,2932 7	53,2173 9	58,9192 5	60,7974 9
22	5	PHBV/ DDGS 75/25	10,956 53	17,4782 6	25,0434 8	29,217 39	33,3913	36,521 75	40,1739 2	45,9130 5	51,6521 8	59,7391 4	66,7826 1
23	1	PHBV	5,9995 7	7,35167	8,47842	10,957 26	12,3093 6	16,140 3	17,0417	22,5352 1	26,5063 9	34,5539 9	35,0696 7
23	2	PHBV- F0	28,544 59	32,3004 6	37,5586 8	44,820 02	49,0766 8	52,081 37	60,5946 7	66,6040 6	72,3630 6	81,3771 4	93,1455 4
23	3	PHBV- SF	9,0140 8	16,0250 3	21,7840 3	25,790 29	34,5539 9	50,078 25	57,8403 7	70,3599 4	75,6181 5	87,3865 4	96,6510 1
23	4	PHBV- pF	11,517 99	18,0281 7	21,0328 6	29,295 77	45,3208 1	56,087 63	65,3521 1	76,1189 3	87,8873 2	89,1392 8	95,1486 7
24	1	PHBV	6,4695 4	10,2570 8	14,0446 1	41,567 35	45,8598 9	50,404 93	54,4449 7	58,485	62,2725 3	65,8075 7	68,8375 9
24	2	PHBV_c	4,4495 3	11,5195 9	14,0446 1	27,427 23	32,4772 7	37,274 81	49,3949 2	53,9399 6	57,98	62,0200 3	69,3426

24	3	PHBV_f	0,4094 9	2,68201	5,45954	10,762 08	15,5596 2	24,902 21	29,9522 5	35,0022 9	40,0523 4	45,1023 8	50,1524 3
24	4	PHBV_v	6,7220 5	9,75207	13,5396 1	18,337 15	23,3871 9	27,679 73	32,7297 7	37,7798 2	42,8298 6	47,8799 1	52,9299 5

Table A13. Overview of the Biodegradation Properties Worksheet of Biodegradation Data Library of scl-
PHA-based formulations.

Study_id	Insta nce	Sample_name	Biodegradation_time (days)										
			5,029 011	8,704062 409	12,9593 759	18,56866 352	22,43713 57	30	33,8491 316	37,9110 244	42,94003 532	47,7756 255	55,8994 26
1	1	PHBV	5,029 011	8,704062 409	12,9593 759	18,56866 352	22,43713 57	30	33,8491 316	37,9110 244	42,94003 532	47,7756 255	55,8994 26
1	2	PLA/PHBV	3,868 472	7,156667 634	11,0251 398	14,70019 134	20,30947 896	30	33,2688 549	37,7176 038	42,94003 532	47,7756 255	55,8994 26
1	3	PHBV	5,656 264	11,89267 129	19,1443 028	25,81580 163	30	39,8839 735	47,8607 681	56,1276 237	67,58520 371	74,9818 657	83,8288 539
1	4	PLA/PHBV	5,656 264	11,89267 129	19,1443 028	25,81580 163	30	39,8839 735	48,4408 898	56,1276 237	68,16533 645	74,8368 352	83,8288 539
2	1	alginic acid treated flax/PHBV	1,996 008	4,291417 166	5,08982 036	6,087824 351	7,085828 343	8,18363 273	9,18163 673	11,0778 443	12,07584 83	14,1716 567	16,0678 643
2	2	untreated flax/PHBV	3,992 016	5,189620 758	6,18762 475	7,185628 743	7,884231 537	9,38123 752	11,1776 447	12,1756 487	14,07185 629	16,1676 647	18,2634 731
2	3	neat PHBV	7,784 43	6,18762	9,98004	13,27345	14,97006	17,2654 7	20,2594 8	23,2534 9	28,24351	30,1397 2	34,1317 4
3	1	PHBV	5,176 470	7,882350	12,2352 90	15,52941 0	19,76471 0	25,4117 60	32,8235 30	36,1176 50	42,47059 0	55,1764 70	62,2352 90
3	2	PHBV-20Vish-E	5,176 47	8,47059	12,0000 0	16,23529	20,58824	25,7647 1	33,4117 6	36,9411 8	43,05882	50,0000 0	54,5882 4

3	3	PHBV-20Vish-V	4,823 53	7,76471	12	15,88235	19,29412	25,6470 6	32,7058 8	36,8235 3	42,82353	49,7647 1	55,0588 2
4	1	PCA20	4,759 92	8,26722	13,2776 6	18,03758	22,79749	26,8058 5	31,8162 8	37,3277 7	43,34029	48,8517 7	54,3632 6
4	2	PCA10	7,265 14	11,77453 0	16,5344 5	20,29228	25,80376	30,5636 7	33,0688 9	37,8288 1	41,08559	45,0939 5	48,3507 3
4	3	PCA	13,52 818	9,51983	18,0375 8	23,29854	27,30689	31,3152 4	38,5803 8	44,0918 6	50,10438	55,6158 7	61,3778 7
4	4	PCA30: PHBV/CaCO3/A TBC/PO	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	1	PHA20W	67,41 796	73,80829	81,1571 7	88,50604	92,97927	102,884 28	98,0915 4	109,594 13	113,4283 2	120,457 69	126,208 98
6	2	PHA20W	73,48 877	80,19862	87,5475	96,17444	107,038	117,901 55	130,682 21	143,782 38	150,4922 3	157,202 07	168,704 66
6	3	PHA50W	75,08 636	78,60104	87,2279 8	95,85492	108,6355 8	116,623 49	126,528 5	136,433 51	152,7288 4	164,550 95	174,455 96
6	4	PHA20W	69,97 409	75,72539	80,8376 5	87,86701	94,57686	101,606 22	112,789 29	121,096 72	129,0846 3	136,113 99	144,101 9
7	1	PHBV	21,43 407	28,92308	35,8956	42,35165	49,32418	56,2967	60,1703 3	63,2692 3	71,27473	77,7307 7	84,4450 5
7	2	PHBV-Q	15,49 451	22,20879	29,4395 6	35,37912	42,86813	50,6153 8	56,5549 5	59,9120 9	62,75275	71,0164 8	77,9890 1
7	3	PHBV-GA	14,71 978	20,4011	29,1813 2	35,8956	42,60989	49,5824 2	56,2967	59,9120 9	62,49451	70,2417 6	77,7307 7
15	1	PHBV	1,189 9	1,73077	1,83894	2,8125	3,13702	3,89423	4,97596	6,05769	7,2476	7,68029	8,00481
15	2	PHBV/TC	1,038 47	1,33053	2,40145	2,98558	3,375	3,47236	3,56972	4,44592	4,9327	5,22476	5,8089
15	3	PHBV/WF	1,081 73	1,83894	3,27765	3,47236	3,86178	4,4351	4,75962	5,94952	6,92308	7,68029	9,119

16	1	PHBV	9,747 08	11,56708	13,3870 8	15,20708	16,93608	18,4830 8	19,9390 8	21,4860 8	22,85108	24,3980 8	25,9450 8
16	2	PHBV/ATBC	14,11 508	15,93508	17,7550 8	19,39308	20,75808	21,9410 8	23,0330 8	24,0340 8	24,94408	25,9450 8	27,6740 8
16	3	PHBV/ATBC/L- CNC	9,929 08	11,74908	13,5690 8	15,38908	17,20908	18,6650 8	19,9390 8	21,1220 8	22,39608	23,5790 8	24,7620 8
16	4	PHBV/ATBC/CaC O3	8,109 08	9,74708	10,9300 8	11,84008	12,65908	13,4780 8	14,2970 8	15,1160 8	16,11708	17,0270 8	17,9370 8
20	1	neat PHBV	5,017 92	12,42533	15,0537 6	20,01195	22,46117	24,9103 9	27,5985 6	29,8685 8	32,67622	35,0059 7	37,3954 6
20	2	phbv sep straw/90:10	7,467 15	12,60454	15,0537 6	17,50299	19,95221	22,5209 1	25,0298 7	27,4193 6	30,16726	32,6164 9	34,8865
20	3	phbv sep straw/80:20	7,586 62	12,5448	15,1135	17,38351	19,83274	22,4611 7	25,0896 1	27,6583 1	30,10753	32,4372 7	35,1254 5
20	4	phbv sep straw/70:30	4,958 18	7,40741	12,5448	14,99403	17,50299	20,0119 5	22,4014 3	25,0896 1	27,53883	29,8088 4	32,6164 9
22	1	PHBV	66,63 717	79,38054	94,5132 8	104,8672 6	118,4070 9	131,946 91	146,283 19	160,619 48	174,1593	188,495 59	209,203 55
22	2	PHBV/Misc 85/15	8,495 58	11,68142	18,8495 6	26,0177	33,9823	45,9292 1	58,6725 7	68,2300 9	87,61059	103,274 34	117,699 13
22	3	PHBV/Misc 75/25	23,00 885	33,9823	41,1504 5	53,09735	66,63717	80,177	95,3097 4	106,194 69	130,0885	147,787 62	157,433 64
22	4	PHBV/ DDGS 85/15	14,07 08	20,44248	31,5929 2	40,70797	53,98232	69,0265 5	81,7699 2	94,5132 8	117,6991 3	138,318 59	154,247 8
22	5	PHBV/ DDGS 75/25	13,27 433	18,58408	29,2035 3	33,6283	40,70797	49,5575	56,6371 7	69,9115 2	84,07081	101,769 93	121,238 91
23	1	PHBV	14,84 319	17,42046	19,9977 3	23,00455	25,86819	29,5909 2	32,8841	37,8636 4	42,62046	46,6136 4	50,9250 1
23	2	PHBV- FO	26,25	28,79546	32,4545 5	36,11364	38,6591	41,3636 4	46,7727 3	50,9090 9	54,56818	60,6136 4	67,7727 3

23	3	PHBV- SF	8,431 82	14,95455	19,5681 8	26,56819	33,56818	41,8409 2	47,0909 1	53,6136 4	61,40909	67,6136 4	74,9318 2
23	4	PHBV- SF	14,15 909	20,52273	25,7727 3	33,25001	42,31819	47,7272 8	53,1363 7	61,4090 9	67,93182	74,4545 4	81,6136 3
24	1	PHBV	24,09 593	28,80524	33,5145 4	61,29943	66,00873	70,7180 3	75,4273 3	80,1366 4	85,0814	89,7907 1	94,5000 1
24	2	PHBV_c	15,38 372	21,97675	26,6860 5	39,1657	43,63954	47,6424 5	59,4157	64,1250 1	68,83431	73,5436 1	84,6104 7
24	3	PHBV_f	9,497 1	14,2064	18,9157	25,27326	29,98256	38,6947 7	42,6976 8	46,7005 9	50,46803	54,4709 4	58,4738 4
24	4	PHBV_v	26,45 059	31,15989	35,3982 6	40,10756	44,34594	47,8779 1	51,6453 5	55,8837 3	59,88663	63,8895 4	67,8924 5

Table A14. Overview of Experimental Biodegradation Data Library of mcl-PHA-based formulations.

Instance	Sample Name	Monomer	mcl_ratio (%)	Additive	Degree_of_Biodegradation (%)	Biodegradation_time (Days)	Degradation_environment	T_biodegradation (Celcius)	Biodegradation_condition
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0	0	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	8,194460425	2	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	8,411467911	5	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	9,193551365	7	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	9,944509164	9	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,44013333	12	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,56455667	14	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,64666777	16	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,84013333	19	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,94056789	23	soil	25	aerobic
1	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	10,99009889	30	soil	25	aerobic
2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0	0	lake water	25	aerobic

2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0,130336336	2	lake water	25	aerobic
2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0,28	16	lake water	25	aerobic
2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0,32	19	lake water	25	aerobic
2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0,533333333	23	lake water	25	aerobic
2	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0,636344949	28	lake water	25	aerobic
3	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	0	0	compost	25	aerobic
3	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	5,06068015	5	compost	25	aerobic
3	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	5,89246552	10	compost	25	aerobic
3	mPHA-9	PHN	100	No	5,99666666	17	compost	25	aerobic

Overview of the Data Libraries for the Mechanical, Thermal and Rheological Properties of scl- and mcl-based formulations.

Table A15. Physicochemical Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of mcl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	initial_scl PHA ratio	initial_3HB ratio	initial_3HV ratio	initial_mcl PHA ratio	3HHx ratio	3HHp ratio	3HO ratio	3HN ratio	3HD ratio	3HUD ratio
51	1	88	88	0	12	12	0	0	0	0	0
51	2	0	0	0	100	2,6	0	17,8	0	23,7	0

51	3	0	0	0	100	2,2	0	15,1	0	26,1	0
51	4	0	0	0	100	2,9	0	18,7	0	27,4	0
51	5	0	0	0	100	2,8	0	17,9	0	24,8	0
51	6	0	0	0	100	2	0	14	0	23,6	0
51	7	0	0	0	100	2,2	0	11,1	0	21,6	0
79	1	0	0	0	100	9	0	89	0	0	0
79	2	0	0	0	100	9	0	89	0	0	0
79	3	0	0	0	100	9	0	89	0	0	0
79	4	0	0	0	100	9	0	89	0	0	0

Study_id	Instance	3HDD ratio	3HTriD ratio	3HTTD ratio	Unsaturated monomer ratio	Uknown monomer ratio	Mw	Mn	Density	Density_units
51	1	0	0	0	0	0	220000	202000	N/A	N/A
51	2	15,7	0	40,2	0	0	100000	80000	N/A	N/A
51	3	17,6	0	39	0	0	157000	108000	N/A	N/A
51	4	19,6	0	31,3	0	0,1	83000	46000	N/A	N/A
51	5	18,6	0	36	0	0	80000	44000	N/A	N/A

51	6	17,4	0	43,1	0	0	89000	56000	N/A	N/A
51	7	16,1	0	49,1	0	0	95000	67000	N/A	N/A
79	1	0	0	0	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
79	2	0	0	0	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
79	3	0	0	0	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
79	4	0	0	0	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Study_id	Instance	PDI	Additive_1	Additive1_type	Additive1_name	Additive1_percentage	Additive_2	Additive2_type	Additive2_name	Additive2_percentage	final_PHA_percentage
51	1	1,09	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	2	1,25	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	3	1,45	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	4	1,82	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	5	1,81	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	6	1,6	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
51	7	1,43	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
79	1	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
79	2	N/A	Yes	Reinforcing_filler	ZnO NPs	1	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	99
79	3	N/A	Yes	Reinforcing_filler	ZnO NPs	2	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	98
79	4	N/A	Yes	Reinforcing_filler	ZnO NPs	4	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	96

Study_id	Instance	formulation_scl_PHA_ratio	formulation_3HB_ratio	formulation_3HV_ratio	formulation_mcl_PHA_ratio	formulation_3HHx_ratio	formulation_3HHp_ratio	formulation_3HO_ratio	formulation_3HN_ratio	formulation_3HD_ratio	formulation_3HUD_ratio	formulation_3HDD_ratio	formulation_3HTriD_ratio	formulation_3HTTD_ratio	formulation_Unsaturated monomer ratio	formulation_Unknown monomer ratio
51	1	88	88	0	12	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
51	2	0	0	0	100	2,6	0	17,8	0	23,7	0	15,7	0	40,2	0	0
51	3	0	0	0	100	2,2	0	15,1	0	26,1	0	17,6	0	39	0	0
51	4	0	0	0	100	2,9	0	18,7	0	27,4	0	19,6	0	31,3	0	0,1
51	5	0	0	0	100	2,8	0	17,9	0	24,8	0	18,6	0	36	0	0
51	6	0	0	0	100	2	0	14	0	23,6	0	17,4	0	43,1	0	0
51	7	0	0	0	100	2,2	0	11,1	0	21,6	0	16,1	0	49,1	0	0
79	1	0	0	0	100	9	0	89	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
79	2	0	0	0	99	8,91	0	88,11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,98
79	3	0	0	0	98	8,82	0	87,22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,96
79	4	0	0	0	96	8,64	0	85,44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,92

Table A16. Physicochemical Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of scl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Monomer_A	Monomer_B	HB_ratio	HV_ratio	HB_ratio_formulation	HV_ratio_formulation	Mw_PHBV	Mn_PHBV	Density
47	1	3HB	3HB	100	0	90	0	490000	N/A	1,25
47	2	3HB	3HV	100	0	88	0	490000	N/A	1,25
47	3	3HB	3HV	100	0	85	0	490000	N/A	1,25
47	4	3HB	3HV	100	0	80	0	490000	N/A	1,25
47	5	3HB	3HV	100	0	75	0	490000	N/A	1,25
93	1	3HB	3HV	100	0	100	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	2	3HB	3HV	100	0	95	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	3	3HB	3HV	100	0	90	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	4	3HB	3HV	100	0	85	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	5	3HB	3HV	100	0	80	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	6	3HB	3HV	100	0	70	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	7	3HB	3HV	100	0	70	0	1416000	N/A	N/A
93	8	3HB	3HV	100	0	70	0	1416000	N/A	N/A

Study_id	Instance	Density_units	PDI	Additive1	Additive1_type	Additive1_name	Additive1_percentage	Additive2	Additive2_type	Additive2_name	Additive2_percentage	PHBV_percentage
47	1	g/cm ³	N/A	Yes	Plasticizer	ATBC	10	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	90
47	2	g/cm ³	N/A	Yes	Plasticizer	ATBC	10	Yes	Reinforcement	CLF	2	88
47	3	g/cm ³	N/A	Yes	Plasticizer	ATBC	10	Yes	Reinforcement	CLF	5	85
47	4	g/cm ³	N/A	Yes	Plasticizer	ATBC	10	Yes	Reinforcement	CLF	10	80
47	5	g/cm ³	N/A	Yes	Plasticizer	ATBC	20	Yes	Reinforcement	CLF	5	75
93	1	N/A	7	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A	N/A	100
93	2	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	4,94	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,06	95
93	3	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	9,94	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,06	90
93	4	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	14,94	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,06	85
93	5	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	19,94	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,06	80
93	6	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	29,94	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,06	70
93	7	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	29,8	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,2	70
93	8	N/A	7	Yes	Plastisizer	mcl_PHA	29,5	Yes	Crosslinking_agent	L-231	0,5	70

Table A17. Thermal Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of scl- and mcl-formulations.

Study_id	Instance	ISO	ASTM	T_mech	T_mech_units	Spread_speed	Spread_units	Morphology	Size_diameter	Size_length	Size_width	Size_thickness	Size_units
44	1	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	2	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	3	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	4	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	5	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	6	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm
44	7	N/A	D882	25	celsius	12,5	mm/min	film	N/A	25	10	N/A	mm

Table A18. Mechanical Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of scl- and mcl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Young_modulus	Tensile_strength	Stress_at_break	Yield_strength	Mechanical_units	Elongation_at_break
44	1	2613,5	27,4	N/A	27,4	Mpa	1,37
44	2	2684,9	22,2	N/A	22,2	Mpa	1,09
44	3	2746,5	21,6	N/A	21,6	Mpa	0,92
44	4	2873,1	20,1	N/A	20,1	Mpa	0,78
44	5	2670,2	27,3	N/A	27,3	Mpa	1,27

44	6	2710,9	27,6	N/A	27,6	Mpa	1,29
44	7	2863,1	27,8	N/A	27,8	Mpa	0,91

Table A19. Thermal Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of scl- and mcl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	Tg 1	Tg 2	Tc1	Tc2	Tm c	Tm1	Tm2	Td5	Tdeg	Temperature _units	DHm 1	DHm 2	DHc 1	DHc 2	Enthaply_ units	Crystallinity
70	1	N/A	N/A	117,2	N/A		173,2	170,3	219,32	N/A	celsius	106,9	107,5	97,1	N/A	J/g	49
70	2	N/A	N/A	113,5	N/A		172,1	169,7	250,32	N/A	celsius	97,8	101,3	91,5	N/A	J/g	48
70	3	N/A	N/A	109,9	N/A		172	168,8	266,64	N/A	celsius	109,3	106,6	95,3	N/A	J/g	46
70	4	N/A	N/A	109,4	N/A		171,2	170,3	223,38	N/A	celsius	91,7	90	81,2	N/A	J/g	42
70	5	N/A	N/A	113,1	N/A		173,2	171,5	255,24	N/A	celsius	94,8	96,1	93,5	N/A	J/g	50
70	6	N/A	N/A	111,5	N/A		172,5	168,6	249,58	N/A	celsius	75,6	78,9	81,5	N/A	J/g	48
70	7	N/A	N/A	111	N/A		171,3	168,2	251,64	N/A	celsius	95,9	90,8	82,5	N/A	J/g	45
90	1	4,98	N/A	78,07	N/A		155,4	166,64	217,15	286,81	celsius	85,59	N/A	62,61	N/A	J/g	59
90	2	4,95	N/A	83,93	N/A		149,89	160,77	222,52	286,87	celsius	83,93	N/A	65,89	N/A	J/g	57
90	4	4,85	N/A	60,55	N/A		138,22	146,94	263,04	288,32	celsius	60,55	N/A	58,06	N/A	J/g	41

Table A20. Rheological Properties in the Material Properties Data Library of scl and mcl- formulations.

Study_id	Instance	complex viscosity (η^*) data points										
41	1	119,746	132,355	132,355	135,031	143,391	149,25	161,695	168,301	171,705	175,177	182,335
41	2	1377,623	1377,623	1433,909	1433,909	1462,909	1433,909	1462,909	1462,909	1433,909	1377,623	1350,314
41	3	17872,031	13776,232	11504,548	9607,462	8692,214	8351,012	7864,157	6973,941	6567,367	6309,573	5823,947
41	4	182334,8	132354,628	86922,145	63095,734	47671,725	35304,177	26673,927	19362,281	16496,481	12715,921	10408,576
41	5	537569,701	390215,349	277637,587	193622,811	135031,404	98017,664	69739,409	50622,994	38247,997	28898,118	22275,43

Study_id	Instance	Test type	constant parameters	geometry	plate diameter	gap size	morphology	diameter	thickness	size units
41	1	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
41	2	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
41	3	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
41	4	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
41	5	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
41	6	DFS	strain,temp	parallel plate	25	0,9	N/A	N/A	1	mm
45	1	DTS	angular frequency,strain	parallel plate	25	N/A	disc	25	2	mm

45	2	DTS	angular frequency, strain	parallel plate	25	N/A	disc	25	2	mm
45	3	DTS	angular frequency, strain	parallel plate	25	N/A	disc	25	2	mm
45	4	DTS	angular frequency, strain	parallel plate	25	N/A	disc	25	2	mm

Study_id	Instance	Angular_frequen cy_units	Temp	Temp_units	Viscosity_units	Modulus_ units	Strain_fixed(%)	Frequency_experim ental_fixed (Hz)
41	1	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
41	2	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
41	3	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
41	4	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
41	5	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
41	6	rad/s	180	celsius	Pa*s	Mpa	1,25	N/A
45	1	hz	N/A	celsius	Pa*s	MPa	0,5	1
45	2	hz	N/A	celsius	Pa*s	MPa	0,5	1
45	3	hz	N/A	celsius	Pa*s	MPa	0,5	1
45	4	hz	N/A	celsius	Pa*s	MPa	0,5	1

Study_id	Instance	Storage_modulus_G' data points										
41	1	0,431	0,829	1,495	2,814	4,854	9,136	15,088	27,188	45,889	79,161	152,293
41	2	98,454	112,219	145,792	189,41	230,49	312,798	406,379	527,956	685,907	853,076	1060,988
41	3	1408,801	1471,615	1537,23	1677,366	1870,636	2377,848	2770,064	3521,151	4574,586	5566,756	6774,114
41	4	15181,9	14220,319	13032,277	11685,815	11187,022	11187,022	10945,667	11433,699	11433,699	12476,012	13913,522

41	5	48234,29	45179,25 9	45179,25 9	43250,84 4	41404,74 1	40511,45 2	37945,56 5	37945,56 5	38782,27 6	39637,43 5	38782, 276
41	6	222031,2 34	222031,2 34	203481,5 48	194796,2 15	182458,3 46	170901,9 25	163607,2 09	156623,8 58	149938,5 81	146703,7 23	137411 ,904

Study_id	Instance	Loss_modulus_G'' data points										
41	1	16,031	18,496	23,587	33,725	49,619	69,939	100	145,041	201,534	284,064	394,706
41	2	102,902	151,399	213,399	305,121	436,266	597,582	806,923	1153,75	1513,99 4	2015,33 8	2682,69 6
41	3	1014,405	1239,275	1513,994	1797,45 6	2259,63	3051,21	3891,00 8	5033,42 2	6418,79 4	8069,23 4	10438,3 91
41	4	10144,04 5	10290,16 6	10588,75 1	10896	11052,9 51	11703,6 95	12216,7 73	12936,0 37	14095,1 05	15358,0 26	17467,7 12
41	5	23926,65 5	22596,29 7	21339,90 8	21339,9 08	21339,9 08	20443,6 77	22596,2 97	22596,2 97	22921,7 86	24620,9 24	27213,3 88
41	6	147130,2 13	125712,6 21	110529,5 14	97180,1 67	94439,8 48	86673,8 72	84229,8 13	77303,4 29	74056,8 47	70946,6 15	68946,0 38

Study_id	Instance	Tandelta data points										
37	1	0,037	0,039	0,042	0,038	0,031	0,029	0,037	0,054	0,072	0,089	0,1
37	2	0,034	0,035	0,038	0,036	0,03	0,027	0,035	0,05	0,066	0,081	0,091
37	3	0,043	0,043	0,044	0,042	0,035	0,031	0,039	0,057	0,076	0,093	0,106
37	4	0,039	0,038	0,042	0,04	0,033	0,031	0,036	0,051	0,067	0,083	0,094
37	5	0,04	0,04	0,043	0,04	0,03	0,028	0,036	0,053	0,071	0,089	0,103
37	6	0,039	0,039	0,041	0,039	0,032	0,03	0,037	0,052	0,068	0,088	0,101

Study_id	Instance	Temperature data points											
37	1	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125
37	2	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125

37	3	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125
37	4	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125
37	5	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125
37	6	-12,5	0	12,5	25	37,5	50	62,5	75	87,5	100	112,5	125

Study_id	Instance	Angular_frequency (ω) data points										
41	1	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188
41	2	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188
41	3	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188
41	4	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188
41	5	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188
41	6	0,1	0,138	0,187	0,249	0,344	0,468	0,628	0,861	1,181	1,607	2,188

